

**Measurement of Direct Photon Cross Section and
Double Helicity Asymmetry at $\sqrt{s} = 510$ GeV
in $\vec{p} + \vec{p}$ Collisions at PHENIX**

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Abstract of the Dissertation

**Measurement of Direct Photon Cross Section and
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Understanding the proton spin decomposition will provide valuable information for the spin structure of the proton. Since the late 1980s, experiments found that only a small portion ($\sim 30\%$) of the proton spin comes from the quark spin. The remaining part of the proton spin must come from the gluon spin, as well as quark and gluon angular momenta. While quark spin contributions were better constrained through polarized lepton-proton scatterings, gluon spin contribution remains less known. Direct photon, jet, and charged pion productions in longitudinally polarized proton collisions ($\vec{p} + \vec{p}$) are good channels to probe the gluon spin. Comparing with jet and charged pion productions, the direct photon production is the “cleanest” channel, since there is little fragmentation involved, and is considered the “golden” channel.

The Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider (RHIC) is the only collider capable of producing collisions between two longitudinally polarized proton beams. Though proposed about three decades ago in the RHIC-spin proposal, this “golden” channel was limited by statistics, until the year 2013 run of RHIC, which provides the largest integrated luminosity (155 pb^{-1}) in $\vec{p} + \vec{p}$ collisions. PHENIX is a detector at the eight o’clock position on the RHIC ring. The

Electromagnetic Calorimeter at PHENIX has fine granularity to separate the two π^0 decay photons up to π^0 transverse momentum p_T of 12 GeV/c, and a shower profile analysis extends the γ/π^0 discrimination to beyond 20 GeV/c. These conditions finally made this “golden” measurement come to reality.

After introducing the collider at RHIC and the detector at PHENIX, I show three main results related to direct photon cross sections: isolated and inclusive direct photon cross sections and their ratio, for photon p_T of 6–30 GeV/c. The next-to-leading-order (NLO) perturbative Quantum Chromodynamics (pQCD) calculations give a consistent prediction for isolated direct photon cross section in this p_T range but underestimate the inclusive direct photon cross section up to a factor of ~ 3 for p_T below 10 GeV/c. This is due to the NLO pQCD calculations only include partonic processes. When the multiparton interactions and parton showers are included in calculations, e.g. in POWHEG + PYTHIA8 simulations, they give more consistent predictions, as also shown in the isolated over inclusive direct photon cross section ratio.

After confirming NLO pQCD calculation gives consistent prediction for the isolated direct photon cross section, I show the isolated direct photon double helicity asymmetry (A_{LL}) for photon p_T of 6–20 GeV/c, and compare it with the NLO pQCD calculation, which gives a consistent prediction. This will be the first published direct photon A_{LL} measurement. When included in future global analyses, it will provide constraints on the gluon spin contributions to the proton spin and help us better understand the spin structure of the proton.

To my parents
for their continuous love

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Publications and Proceedings

1. Zhongling Ji for PHENIX Collaboration. Measurement of Direct Photon Cross Section and Double Helicity Asymmetry at $\sqrt{s} = 510$ GeV in $\vec{p} + \vec{p}$ Collisions at PHENIX. *Preparing to submit to Phys. Rev. Lett.* (2021).
2. Zhongling Ji for PHENIX Collaboration. Longitudinal double helicity asymmetry A_{LL} from direct photon, jet and charged pion production in polarized $\vec{p} + \vec{p}$ collisions. *Submitted to SciPost Physics Proceedings* (2021).
3. Zhongling Ji and Kenneth N. Barish for PHENIX Collaboration. Direct photon cross section and double helicity asymmetry at mid-rapidity in $\vec{p} + \vec{p}$ collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 510$ GeV. *PoS (SPIN2018)*, 128 (2018).
4. Zhongling Ji and Shaoyan Gao. Two-Photon Scattering by a Cavity-Coupled Two-Level Emitter in a One-Dimensional Waveguide. *Opt. Comm.*, 285, 1302 (2012).

Chapter 1

Gluon Spin inside Proton

1.1 From Quark Model to QCD

Between 1908 and 1913, Hans Geiger and Ernest Marsden performed the Rutherford gold foil experiment [1–3], which discovered that every atom has a nucleus where all of its positive charge and most of its mass is concentrated. Ernest Rutherford named the hydrogen nucleus as proton in 1920. After James Chadwick discovered neutron in 1932 [4], models for a nucleus composed of protons and neutrons were quickly developed by Dmitri Iwanenko and Werner Heisenberg. Due to this reason, protons and neutrons are together called nucleons (see [5]). In 1934, Hideki Yukawa predicted the existence of the meson as the carrier of the nuclear force that holds atomic nuclei together [6]. The first meson, called pion later, was discovered in 1947, by Cecil Powell, César Lattes, and Giuseppe Occhialini [7]. The Yukawa theory (see [8, 9]), formulated the interactions between nucleons through pions, by using the global SU(2) isospin symmetry, where nucleons are in the fundamental representation **2** and pions are in the adjoint representation **3**, with the following Lagrangian density

$$\mathcal{L} = \bar{\psi}(i\not{\partial} - mI + ig_{\pi}\gamma^5\vec{\pi} \cdot \vec{\tau})\psi + \frac{1}{2} [(\partial_{\mu}\vec{\pi})^2 - \mu^2\vec{\pi}^2] - \lambda(\vec{\pi}^2)^2, \quad (1.1)$$

where $\vec{\tau}$ are Pauli matrices, ψ and π are nucleon and pion fields

$$\psi = \begin{pmatrix} \psi_p \\ \psi_n \end{pmatrix}, \quad \pi = \begin{pmatrix} \pi_1 \\ \pi_2 \\ \pi_3 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \pi^{\pm} = \frac{\pi_1 \mp i\pi_2}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad \pi^0 = \pi_3. \quad (1.2)$$

With the large number of lighter hadrons that were being discovered starting in the 1950s and continuing through the 1960s, it becomes necessary to have a classification scheme to organize them. The successful flavor SU(3) quark model was independently proposed by Murray Gell-Mann [10] and George Zweig. This model enlarges the SU(2) isospin group to SU(3) flavor group. The mesons sit in the adjoint representation $\mathbf{8}$. The baryons can sit in either $\mathbf{8}$ or $\mathbf{10}$ representation. With the SU(3) breaking, the Gell-Mann-Okubo relation successfully predicted the Ω^- mass. The above description of SU(3) in terms of baryons and mesons becomes simpler when re-expressed in terms of the three lightest quarks, u, d, and s. From Young tableau, we know

$$\mathbf{3} \otimes \bar{\mathbf{3}} = \mathbf{1} \oplus \mathbf{8}, \quad (1.3)$$

$$\mathbf{3} \otimes \mathbf{3} \otimes \mathbf{3} = \mathbf{1} \oplus \mathbf{8} \oplus \mathbf{8} \oplus \mathbf{10}. \quad (1.4)$$

A meson in $\mathbf{8}$ is made up of a quark in $\mathbf{3}$ and an antiquark in $\bar{\mathbf{3}}$. A baryon in $\mathbf{8}$ or $\mathbf{10}$ is made up of three quarks in $\mathbf{3}$.

The original quark model includes only spin and flavor quantum numbers but no color quantum numbers. Since quark has spin 1/2, this leads to a situation that violates the Fermi-Dirac statistics. For example, Δ^{++} baryon is one of the lightest excited states of the nucleon and has spin 3/2 and charge +2, which is interpreted as a uuu bound state with zero orbital angular momentum and all three quark spins parallel. Without additional quantum numbers, this certainly violates the Pauli exclusion principle since all three quarks have the same quantum numbers. To reconcile the baryon spectrum with the spin-statistics theorem, Greenberg [11] and Han and Nambu [12] proposed that quarks carry an additional, unobserved quantum number, called color, in which baryon wavefunctions must be totally antisymmetric. As a result, the quark wavefunctions are totally symmetric in spin and flavor and totally antisymmetric in color, in agreement with Fermi-Dirac statistics.

The introduction of a color degree of freedom also explains how quarks bind together to form hadrons, by promoting the global color SU(3) symmetry to a local symmetry. This is the work done by Yang and Mills in 1954 [13], though original for SU(2) isospin symmetry. The Yang-Mills theory based on local color SU(3) symmetry is a non-abelian gauge theory, of which the gauge bosons are called gluons. It has asymptotic freedom, which means at high energy the interaction is very weak, as well as color confinement, which means the long-distance interaction is very strong. The former explains the

Bjorken scaling in deep inelastic scattering. The latter explains why we only see the color singlet hadrons but no quarks and gluons at a large distance. The strong force that binds nucleons together can be taken as the residual color force.

The above theory, which describes the interactions between quarks and gluons through the color force mediated by gluons, is called Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD) (see [8,9]), with the Lagrangian density

$$\mathcal{L} = \bar{\psi}(i\not{D} - m)\psi - \frac{1}{4}(G_{\mu\nu}^a)^2 + \frac{1}{2\xi}(\partial^\mu A_\mu^a)^2 + (\partial^\mu b^a)(D_\mu c)^a, \quad (1.5)$$

where $D_\mu = \partial_\mu - igA_\mu^a t^a$ and $G_{\mu\nu}^a = \partial_\mu A_\nu^a - \partial_\nu A_\mu^a + gf^{abc}A_\mu^a A_\nu^b$. The classical Lagrangian density only contains $\bar{\psi}(i\not{D} - m)\psi - \frac{1}{4}(G_{\mu\nu}^a)^2$. But to quantize it, we need to do the Feynman path integral over the gluon field A_μ^a . Then we need the Faddeev-Popov gauge fixing term $\frac{1}{2\xi}(\partial^\mu A_\mu^a)^2$ and the ghost term $(\partial^\mu b^a)(D_\mu c)^a$ from Jacobian determinant [14].

One way to calculate the QCD Feynman path integral is to expand the integrand over the coupling constant g , under the assumption that $g \ll 1$ (see [8,9]). This works for energy larger than several GeV due to asymptotic freedom but fails for low energy. There are rich non-perturbative properties of QCD that are not contained in the perturbative expansion. To uncover them, we need resummation tools, lattice calculations [15], or even to abandon the first principle and base on phenomenological assumptions, or other methods.

1.2 Proton Spin Decomposition

The easiest way to do QCD Feynman path integral is expanding the integrand over the coupling constant g , which requires g to be small. To reach this kinetic range and test QCD directly, we accelerate hadrons to high energy ($\gg 10$ GeV) and collide them, then analyze the collision products. However, even this high energy cross section cannot be perturbatively calculated, due to the infrared (IR) and collinear divergences associated with the initial and final state hadrons. The solution is to factorize the hard processes, which can be calculated perturbatively, from soft processes. Since the hard and soft processes are related to short- and long-distance physics respectively, the cross section can be expressed as the products of their probabilities (rather than amplitudes) due to causality. This QCD factorization theorem [16]

states that the cross section can be expressed as

$$Q^2 \sigma_{phys}(Q, m, f) = \hat{\sigma}(Q/\mu, \alpha_s(\mu), f) \otimes f_{LD}(\mu, m) + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{Q^p}\right), \quad (1.6)$$

where σ_{phys} ($\hat{\sigma}$) is the physical (parton) cross section. Q and m define hard and soft scales, respectively. μ is the factorization scale. f_{LD} is called parton distribution function (PDF) for initial states or fragmentation function (FF) for final states, which describes the long-distance physics and is universal for any inclusive processes.

The leading order PDF has a physical meaning: $f_{q/A}(x)dx$ is the probability to find a parton q with momentum xP_μ to $(x+dx)P_\mu$, where P_μ is the momentum of hadron A . In operator definition

$$f_{q/A}(x) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int d\xi^- e^{-ixP^+\xi^-} \langle P | \bar{\psi}(0, \xi^-, 0_\perp) \gamma^+ W(\xi^-, 0) \psi(0, 0, 0_\perp) | P \rangle, \quad (1.7)$$

$$f_{g/A}(x) = \frac{1}{2\pi x P^+} \int d\xi^- e^{-ixP^+\xi^-} \langle P | G^{+\nu}(0, \xi^-, 0_\perp) W(\xi^-, 0) G_\nu^+(0, 0, 0_\perp) | P \rangle, \quad (1.8)$$

where $|P\rangle$ is the hadron state and ψ (G) is the quark (gluon) field. The Wilson line (gauge link) with the connection A^+ in the fundamental (adjoint) representation for the quark (gluon) distribution is defined as

$$W(\xi^-, 0) = P \exp \left(ig \int_0^{\xi^-} d\zeta^- A^+ \right). \quad (1.9)$$

In light cone gauge, we have $A^+ = 0 \Rightarrow W(\xi^-, 0) = 0$.

The above definitions can be extended to the case with spin [17]. In light cone gauge

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta q(x) &= \frac{1}{4\pi} \int d\xi^- e^{-ixP^+\xi^-} \langle P, S | (\psi^{+R})^\dagger(\xi^-) \psi^{+R}(0) - (\psi^{+L})^\dagger(\xi^-) \psi^{+L}(0) | P, S \rangle \\ &\Rightarrow \Delta q \equiv \int_0^1 dx \Delta q(x) = \frac{1}{2M} \langle P, S | \bar{\psi}(0) \gamma^+ \gamma^5 \psi(0) | P, S \rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (1.10)$$

where M and S^μ are proton mass and spin, respectively. Δq is quark contribution to the proton spin. Similarly, for gluon contribution we have

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta g(x) &= \frac{i}{2\pi x P^+} \int d\xi^- e^{-ixP^+\xi^-} \langle P, S | G^{+R}(\xi^-) G_R^+(0) - G^{+L}(\xi^-) G_L^+(0) | P, S \rangle \\ \Rightarrow \Delta g &\equiv \int_0^1 dx \Delta g(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}M} \langle P, S | A^\nu(\infty) \tilde{G}_\nu^+(0) - A^\nu(0) \tilde{G}_\nu^+(0) | P, S \rangle.\end{aligned}\tag{1.11}$$

The first term is a surface term and the second term is the forward matrix element of the gluonic Chern-Simons current K^+ .

We can also define the total angular momentum from quarks and gluons by using the energy-momentum tensor [18]

$$J_{q,g}^i = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon^{ijk} \int d^3x (T_{q,g}^{0k} x^j - T_{q,g}^{0j} x^k).\tag{1.12}$$

Since we already defined the quark spin Δq and gluon spin Δg , their orbital angular momentum can be defined as

$$\vec{L}_{q,g} \equiv \vec{J}_{q,g} - \vec{S}_{q,g}.\tag{1.13}$$

Finally, we have the proton spin decomposition

$$\frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{2} \Delta q + \Delta g + L_q + L_g.\tag{1.14}$$

The work of this thesis is to understand the gluon spin contribution Δg to the proton spin.

1.3 Experiments Studying the Proton Spin

1.3.1 DIS Experiments

The first experiments used polarized deep inelastic scattering (DIS) to study the proton spin. They collided polarized leptons with molecules or atoms containing polarized protons or deuterons [19].

The SLAC experiments performed a series of polarized DIS measurements, including E80 [20, 21] and E130 [22, 23] from 1976 to 1983, E142 [24] and E143 [25] from 1992 to 1993, and E154 [26] and E155 [27, 28] from 1995 to 1999. The beam was composed of longitudinally polarized electrons

produced by laser photoemission and subsequently accelerated. Its polarization was measured by Møller scattering $e^-e^- \rightarrow e^-e^-$ and was about 80%. Scattered electrons were detected with magnetic spectrometers for high-momentum resolution and good electron identification. The polarized proton targets were made up of solid-state butanol and ammonia (NH_3). The polarized deuteron targets included D-butanol, ND_3 , and ^6LiD [29, 30]. The target material was cooled down to ~ 1 K, held in strong magnetic fields, and polarized using dynamic nuclear polarization. The ^3He target was polarized using optical pumping and adiabatic spin exchange. The target polarization was measured by the NMR technique. For E154 and E155 experiments, the target polarization was typically 38% for ^3He , 90% for NH_3 , and 22% for ^6LiD . The typical values of dilution factor from nonpolarizable nucleons for polarized solid-state targets range from 0.1 to 0.2 with an exception of ^6LiD (0.4–0.5). These values should be used when extracting physical observables from the measured ones. The neutron information was obtained either from the combination of measurements with proton and deuteron targets or from polarized ^3He target. Since in ^3He the two proton spins are antialigned, its contribution is dominated by the neutron. The polarization directions of the beam and the target were frequently inverted to reduce systematic uncertainties in spin-asymmetry measurements.

The EMC [31, 32], SMC [33–39], and COMPASS [40, 41] experiments at CERN used polarized muon beam in polarized DIS. The EMC experiment in 1985 used the muon beam up to 200 GeV and a solid-state irradiated ammonia target. It can reach Bjorken- x down to 0.01, which is due to the high energy reached by the muon beam. These low- x measurements showed that not only valence quarks but also sea quarks and gluons contribute to the nucleon spin. The subsequent SMC experiments were performed from 1992 to 1996 and extended the x range down to 0.004 for $Q^2 > 1 \text{ GeV}^2$. These experiments used polarized proton from butanol and ammonia targets and polarized neutron from D-butanol targets and extracted the isovector Bjorken sum rule for $g_1^p - g_1^n$. The SMC spectrometer had large acceptance in the forward region and provided for the first time the information of quark distributions for different flavors in semi-inclusive DIS. The COMPASS experiment used a polarized muon beam from the weak decay of the parent pions produced by the primary proton beam of 400 GeV. Due to the parity violation in the weak decay, the muon beam got a polarization of about 80%. An advantage of the muon beams over electron beams is the high muon energy. However, the muon beams had lower beam intensity compared to

electron beams. Due to this reason, gas targets cannot be used. Instead, the solid-state targets were cooled down to about 60 mK in frozen spin mode and polarized by dynamic nuclear polarization. The proton and neutron targets used irradiated ammonia (NH_3) and lithium-6 deuteride (${}^6\text{LiD}$), respectively. Since lithium-6 is very close to a free deuteron and a helium-4 core, ${}^6\text{LiD}$ is equivalent to two deuterons and a helium nucleus. The typical polarizations are 85% for protons and 50% for deuterons. To reduce systematic uncertainties in spin-asymmetry measurements, interleaved target polarizations were used in two or three cells: “ \rightarrow, \leftarrow ” with 60 cm for each cell in two-cell configuration before 2004 and “ $\rightarrow, \leftarrow, \rightarrow$ ” with 30, 60, 30 cm for each cell in three-cell configuration after 2006. The target spin polarizations were inverted by adiabatically tuning the magnetic field typically once per day. The COMPASS experiment focused on inclusive and semi-inclusive DIS. In addition, to measure the scattered muon to reconstruct the kinematics, the detection of a hadron in the final state provides information about the flavor of the struck quark.

The HERMES experiment at DESY from 1995 to 2007 used polarized hydrogen or deuterium atoms as the gas targets [42]. Compared with the previous compound targets with dilution from unpolarized nucleons, these pure nuclear-polarized targets provide essentially background-free measurements with little or no dilution. In this way, the main systematic uncertainty from the dilution factor is eliminated. The target polarization was $\sim 85\%$ ($\sim 75\%$) for longitudinal (transverse) polarized targets. The direction of polarization can be inverted within milliseconds to reduce systematic uncertainties in spin-asymmetry measurements. To increase the target density, the gas was fed into a T-shaped open-ended elliptical cell coaxial to the lepton beam [43]. The gas atoms bounced on the wall several hundred times. As a result, the effective gas density was increased ~ 100 times compared to the gas jet targets. The polarization of a sample of the gas target was measured by Breit-Rabi polarimeter [44]. A gas analyzer was used to determine the relative amount of atomic and molecular hydrogen or deuterium from a sample of gas target [45]. The cell was kept at about 100 K and in a surrounding magnetic field to prevent spin relaxation and wall collisions. The HERA lepton storage ring provided electron or positron beams of typically 40 mA with an energy of 27.5 GeV. The electron beam was spontaneously polarized in the emission of synchrotron radiation through Sokolov-Ternov effect [46] and grows and asymptotically approaches an equilibrium after typically a half hour. The beam polarization can be as large as 60%. Spin rotators

were used before and after collision points and one of the two polarimeters to rotate the transverse polarization to longitudinal polarization [47–50]. The beam polarimeters used Compton backscattering from circularly polarized laser light to measure the electron polarization. The HERMES detector can detect the scattered lepton and produced hadrons within a wide angular acceptance and with good momentum resolution. It has the ability to separate pions, kaons, and protons over almost the whole momentum range.

Experiments at Jefferson Laboratory (JLab) performed polarized DIS by using the Continuous Electron Beam Accelerator Facility (CEBAF) [51], which produced electron beams with 85% polarization. The initial energy ranged from 0.8 to 6 GeV, with a later upgrade to 12 GeV [52]. The polarized electrons were generated by circularly polarized photons from high-intensity laser illuminating on a thin gallium arsenide (GaAs) layer on top of GaAs-phosphide bulk matter [53, 54]. The electrons were accelerated five times by each of the two antiparallel linear accelerators, which are connected by two recirculation arcs. The spin direction was manipulated by Wien filters and inverted about every 30 ms. The electron beams were delivered to four Halls named A, B, C, and D with different energies. Hall B used longitudinal polarized solid-state ammonia (NH_3) targets for the proton and ND_3 for the deuteron [55]. Hall A used polarized ^3He target and measured its polarization by NMR technique [56]. Hall A and C were equipped with small acceptance spectrometers with high resolution [57], while Hall B and D were instrumented with large acceptance detectors [58].

The Electron-Ion Collider (EIC) is a new project for polarized DIS and recently passed Critical Decision Zero and One (CD-0 and CD-1) by the US Department of Energy (DOE) [59]. It will be built at BNL and partly use the RHIC ring. It will provide highly polarized electron ($\sim 70\%$) and proton ($\sim 70\%$) beams, as well as ion beams from deuterons to heavy nuclei such as gold, lead, or uranium. The $e + p$ center-of-mass energy will range from 20 to 100 GeV, with a future upgrade to 140 GeV. EIC will provide intensive beam with high luminosity of $10^{33} - 10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$. There will be more than one interaction point built on the collider. The physical goals of EIC are to study the 3D structures of nucleons with high luminosity beam, to explore gluon saturation at small Bjorken- x , and to test the Standard Model (SM) with precision frontier. The gluon spin contribution to the proton spin will also be explored in EIC through photon-gluon fusion processes (see Fig. 1.2).

Figure 1.1: Kinematics of deep inelastic scattering.

1.3.2 Hadron Scattering Experiments

Instead of polarized DIS, proton spin can also be explored by hadron scattering. The Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider (RHIC) at Brookhaven National Laboratory (BNL) is the only collider that provides polarized proton beams. At RHIC, longitudinally or transversely polarized proton beams were collided with center-of-mass energy from 62.4 to 510 GeV. PHENIX and STAR are two major detectors at RHIC. The details of RHIC and PHENIX will be described in Ch. 2 and Ch. 3, respectively. There are many channels to probe the gluon spin contribution, including direct photon, jet, and charged pion productions. Their (dis)advantages are discussed in Sec. 1.5.

1.4 Proton Spin Puzzle

Polarized deep inelastic scattering (DIS) provides a way to probe the quark and gluon spin contribution to the proton spin. The kinematics of DIS is shown in Fig. 1.1. The amplitudes of DIS can be separated into a leptonic part and a hadronic part. Let $J_\mu(z)$ denote the electromagnetic current in QCD. The forward scattering amplitude of the hadronic part is

$$T_{\mu\nu}(q, P) = i \int d^4z e^{iq \cdot z} \langle P, S | T(J_\mu(z) J_\nu(0)) | P, S \rangle. \quad (1.15)$$

If we define $Q^2 \equiv -q^2$, the spin-independent and spin-dependent parts of $T_{\mu\nu}$ are

$$\begin{aligned} T_{\mu\nu}^S &= \frac{1}{2}(T_{\mu\nu} + T_{\nu\mu}) \\ &= -T_1(g_{\mu\nu} + \frac{q_\mu q_\nu}{Q^2}) + \frac{1}{M^2}T_2(P_\mu + \frac{P \cdot q}{Q^2}q_\mu)(P_\nu + \frac{P \cdot q}{Q^2}q_\nu) \end{aligned} \quad (1.16)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} T_{\mu\nu}^A &= \frac{1}{2}(T_{\mu\nu} - T_{\nu\mu}) \\ &= \frac{i}{M^2}\epsilon_{\mu\nu\lambda\sigma}q^\lambda \left[S^\sigma(A_1 + \frac{\nu}{M}A_2) - \frac{1}{M^2}S \cdot q P^\sigma A_2 \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (1.17)$$

Here $\nu = P \cdot q/M$ and $\epsilon_{0123} = +1$; the proton spin vector is normalized to $S^2 = -1$. The form-factors T_1 , T_2 , A_1 and A_2 are functions of ν and Q^2 . From optical theorem, the inclusive photon-proton scattering amplitude is

$$W_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\pi}\text{Im}T_{\mu\nu}. \quad (1.18)$$

The spin-independent and spin-dependent parts of $W_{\mu\nu}$ are

$$W_{\mu\nu}^S = -W_1(g_{\mu\nu} + \frac{q_\mu q_\nu}{Q^2}) + \frac{1}{M^2}W_2(P_\mu + \frac{P \cdot q}{Q^2}q_\mu)(P_\nu + \frac{P \cdot q}{Q^2}q_\nu) \quad (1.19)$$

and

$$W_{\mu\nu}^A = \frac{i}{M^2}\epsilon_{\mu\nu\lambda\sigma}q^\lambda \left[S^\sigma(G_1 + \frac{\nu}{M}G_2) - \frac{1}{M^2}S \cdot q P^\sigma G_2 \right]. \quad (1.20)$$

The cross sections for the absorption of a transversely polarized photon with spin polarized parallel $\sigma_{\frac{3}{2}}$ and anti-parallel $\sigma_{\frac{1}{2}}$ to the spin of the longitudinally polarized proton target are

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{\frac{3}{2}} &= \frac{4\pi^2\alpha}{\sqrt{\nu^2 + Q^2}} \left[W_1 - \frac{\nu}{M^2}G_1 + \frac{Q^2}{M^3}G_2 \right], \\ \sigma_{\frac{1}{2}} &= \frac{4\pi^2\alpha}{\sqrt{\nu^2 + Q^2}} \left[W_1 + \frac{\nu}{M^2}G_1 - \frac{Q^2}{M^3}G_2 \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (1.21)$$

In high Q^2 deep inelastic scattering the structure functions exhibit approximate scaling. One finds

$$\begin{aligned}
MW_1(\nu, Q^2) &\rightarrow F_1(x, Q^2), \\
\nu W_2(\nu, Q^2) &\rightarrow F_2(x, Q^2), \\
\frac{\nu}{M}G_1(\nu, Q^2) &\rightarrow g_1(x, Q^2), \\
\frac{\nu^2}{M^2}G_2(\nu, Q^2) &\rightarrow g_2(x, Q^2).
\end{aligned} \tag{1.22}$$

The structure functions F_1 , F_2 , g_1 and g_2 are to a very good approximation independent of Q^2 and depend only on x . The small Q^2 dependence which is present in these structure functions is logarithmic. The double-spin asymmetry from polarized DIS can probe the g_1 structure function

$$\mathcal{A}_1 = \frac{\sigma_{\frac{1}{2}} - \sigma_{\frac{3}{2}}}{\sigma_{\frac{1}{2}} + \sigma_{\frac{3}{2}}} = \frac{M\nu G_1 - Q^2 G_2}{M^3 W_1} = \frac{g_1 - \frac{Q^2}{\nu^2} g_2}{F_1} \rightarrow \frac{g_1}{F_1}. \tag{1.23}$$

By using the dispersion relation, we can get the g_1 spin sum rules in polarized DIS

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_0^1 dx g_1^p(x, Q^2) &= \left(\frac{1}{12} g_A^{(3)} + \frac{1}{36} g_A^{(8)} \right) \left\{ 1 + \sum_{\ell \geq 1} c_{\text{NS}\ell} \alpha_s^\ell(Q) \right\} \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{9} g_A^{(0)}|_{\text{inv}} \left\{ 1 + \sum_{\ell \geq 1} c_{\text{S}\ell} \alpha_s^\ell(Q) \right\} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{Q^2}\right) + \beta_\infty
\end{aligned} \tag{1.24}$$

where β_∞ represents a possible leading-power subtraction constant and

$$\begin{aligned}
g_A^{(3)} &= \Delta u - \Delta d, \\
g_A^{(8)} &= \Delta u + \Delta d - 2\Delta s, \\
g_A^{(0)} &\equiv g_A^{(0)}|_{\text{inv}}/E(\alpha_s) = \Delta u + \Delta d + \Delta s
\end{aligned} \tag{1.25}$$

are the isovector, octet and singlet axial charges in terms of the flavor dependent axial-charges (in light cone gauge they are Eq. 1.10)

$$2MS_\mu \Delta q = \langle P, S | \bar{q} \gamma_\mu \gamma_5 q | P, S \rangle \tag{1.26}$$

and

$$E(\alpha_s) = \exp \int_0^{\alpha_s} d\tilde{\alpha}_s \gamma(\tilde{\alpha}_s) / \beta(\tilde{\alpha}_s) \tag{1.27}$$

is a renormalization group factor which corrects for the non-zero anomalous dimension $\gamma(\alpha_s)$.

In late 1980s, European Muon Collaboration (EMC) measured the g_1^p structure function [31]. $g_A^{(0)}$ can be extracted from g_1^p by using Eq. 1.24 with the assumption that $\beta_\infty = 0$ at leading power, where $g_A^{(3)}$ can be measured from the difference of g_1 between proton and neutron $g_1^p - g_1^n$, and $g_A^{(8)}$ can be measured from hyperon β decays. Recently, COMPASS measured [41]

$$g_A^{(0)}|_{\text{pDIS}, Q^2 \rightarrow \infty} = 0.33 \pm 0.03(\text{stat.}) \pm 0.05(\text{syst.}). \quad (1.28)$$

Form Eq. 1.25 that $g_A^{(0)} = \Delta u + \Delta d + \Delta s$, it seems that these measurements mean that the quark spin only contributes to $\sim 30\%$ of the proton spin. This is very different from the static quark model, of which the simple $SU(6) = SU(3)_{\text{color}} \times SU(2)_{\text{spin}}$ proton wave function

$$\begin{aligned} |p \uparrow\rangle = & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}|u \uparrow (ud)_{S=0}\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{18}}|u \uparrow (ud)_{S=1}\rangle - \frac{1}{3}|u \downarrow (ud)_{S=1}\rangle \\ & - \frac{1}{3}|d \uparrow (uu)_{S=1}\rangle + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{3}|d \downarrow (uu)_{S=1}\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (1.29)$$

yields $g_A^{(0)} = 1$. A relativistic quark model, such as the MIT bag model, solves the Dirac equations of a quark confined in a spherical region and includes the orbital angular momentum of the quark. It predicts that $g_A^{(0)} \sim 0.6$, which is still about twice of the measured $g_A^{(0)}$. This discrepancy between measurements and theoretical predictions is called the proton spin puzzle.

The solution of the proton spin puzzle is by noting that the definition of the $g_A^{(0)}$ (Eq. 1.25) comes from the axial-vector current of the quarks $\bar{q}\gamma_\mu\gamma_5q$ (Eq. 1.4), which is not conserved even for massless quarks due to axial anomaly

$$\partial^\mu(\bar{q}\gamma_\mu\gamma_5q) = 2im\bar{q}\gamma_5q + \frac{\alpha_s}{4\pi}G_{\mu\nu}\tilde{G}^{\mu\nu}. \quad (1.30)$$

As a result, the gluon spin Δg (Eq. 1.11) contribute to $g_A^{(0)}$ as

$$g_A^{(0)} = \sum_q \Delta q - 3\frac{\alpha_s}{2\pi}\Delta g + \mathcal{C}_\infty, \quad (1.31)$$

where \mathcal{C}_∞ denotes a potential nonperturbative gluon topological contribution with support only at Bjorken $x = 0$. What a relativistic quark model calculates is $\sum_q \Delta q + \mathcal{C}_\infty$. However, what a polarized DIS experiment measures is

Figure 1.2: Production of a $c\bar{c}$ pair in polarized photon-gluon fusion is being used to measure gluon polarization in the polarized proton.

$\sum_q \Delta q - 3\frac{\alpha_s}{2\pi} \Delta g$. Then the difference between measurements and theoretical predictions is $-3\frac{\alpha_s}{2\pi} \Delta g + \mathcal{C}_\infty$. Besides the topological effect at Bjorken $x = 0$, understanding the gluon spin contribution Δg is important to resolve the proton spin puzzle.

1.5 Direct Photon as the “Golden” Channel

Polarized DIS can probe the gluon spin Δg at next-to-leading (NLO) order through photon-gluon fusion process (Fig. 1.2). To probe Δg at leading order, we need polarized proton-proton collisions (Fig. 1.3). Unlike hadrons and jets production, which largely include the fragmentation processes, there is little fragmentation involved with direct photon production, so this is a very “clean” channel. Since the quark-gluon Compton scattering is linear to the gluon parton distribution function (PDF), this process also probes the sign of the gluon spin Δg . With these advantages, the direct photon production in pp collisions is also called the “golden” channel. The leading power differential cross section for inclusive direct photon production in p+p

(a) Quark-gluon Compton scattering.

(b) Quark-antiquark annihilation.

(c) Quark fragmentation to photon.

(d) Quark bremsstrahlung.

Figure 1.3: Samples of direct photon productions in polarized proton-proton collisions.

collision is [60]

$$\begin{aligned}
E_\gamma \frac{d^3\sigma^{p+p\rightarrow\gamma+X}}{dp_\gamma^3} &= \sum_{a,b} \int_{x_A}^1 dx_1 f_{a/p}(x_1, \mu_f) \int_{x_B}^1 dx_2 f_{b/p}(x_2, \mu_f) \\
&\times \sum_{c=\gamma,q,\bar{q},g} \int_{z_{min}}^1 \frac{dz}{z^2} D_{\gamma/c}(z, \mu_F) E_\gamma \frac{d^3\hat{\sigma}^{a+b\rightarrow c+X}(p_\gamma, x_1, x_2, z, \mu_R, \mu_f, \mu_F)}{dp_\gamma^3},
\end{aligned} \tag{1.32}$$

where $\hat{\sigma}$'s are the corresponding partonic cross sections. The functions f and D are parton distribution and fragmentation functions, respectively. The parameters μ_R, μ_f, μ_F are renormalization, initial-state factorization and final-state factorization scales, respectively. The integration limits x_A, x_B, z_{min} are fixed by kinematics.

We can also add an isolation cut (Sec. 4.5) to increase the signal-to-background ratio and suppress the fragmentation process [60, 61]. The isolated direct photon cross section is shown to have infrared and collinear safety, as well as initial and final-state collinear factorizability in [61]. The isolated direct photon cross section is calculated as the inclusive one with subtraction due to isolation cut, which depends on isolation cone angle R and hadron energy fraction limit ϵ_h .

Similarly, the polarized gluon PDF inside the proton can be extracted from the polarized direct photon cross section

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta\sigma^{\vec{p}+\vec{p}\rightarrow\gamma+X} &\sim \sum_{abc} \Delta f_{a/p}(x_1, \mu_f) \otimes \Delta f_{b/p}(x_2, \mu_f) \\
&\otimes \Delta D_{\gamma/c}(z, \mu_F) \otimes \Delta\hat{\sigma}^{a+b\rightarrow c+X}(p_\gamma, x_1, x_2, z, \mu_R, \mu_f, \mu_F)
\end{aligned} \tag{1.33}$$

in polarized $\vec{p}+\vec{p}$ collisions. The \otimes represent convolutions as in Eq. 1.32. The functions Δf and ΔD are polarized parton distribution and fragmentation functions, respectively.

Chapter 2

Polarized Protons at RHIC

2.1 RHIC Overview

The Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider (RHIC) (Fig. 2.1) is an accelerator located at Brookhaven National Laboratory (BNL). It has two acceleration pipes, named blue and yellow beam, to accelerate a vast kind of particles, including proton, deuteron, helium, aluminum, copper, gold, and uranium. The main purpose of heavy ion collisions is to study the property of quark gluon plasma (QGP), while the proton and deuteron collisions provide a baseline for it. The hadron collisions are also important to study the effects of cold nuclear matter, as well as the structure of proton spin if the beam(s) is(are) polarized. RHIC is the only facility to accelerate polarized protons, ranging from 62.4 to 510 GeV of center-of-mass energy. There are four interaction points (IP) on RHIC and two of them are still taking data (PHENIX stopped taking data after 2016 and is undergoing an upgrade to sPHENIX). PHENIX detector is an IP and located at the eight o'clock position on the RHIC ring.

2.2 Proton Source from OPPIS

The polarized proton beams are generated by the RHIC Optically Pumped Polarized Ion Source (OPPIS) (Fig. 2.2). Initially, low-pressure H_2 gas is injected into a volume, in which there are also 1 T magnetic field and 29.2 GHz microwaves. The frequency of the microwaves is corresponding to the electron cyclotron frequency in the magnetic field $f = \frac{eB}{2\pi m_e}$. Through this

Figure 2.1: Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider.

Figure 2.2: The RHIC OPPIS system.

electron cyclotron resonance (ECR) method the H_2 molecules are ionized to H^+ ions. Then the H^+ ions go through an Rb gas cell, which is optically pumped by a 795 nm pulsed laser beam. The H^+ ion acquires an electron with spin polarization ($m_J = +1/2$) when colliding with the Rb gas. After the Rb-cell, electron-spin polarized H^0 atoms are produced.

The electron spin of the H^0 atom is transferred to the proton spin through Sona transition [62]. Fig. 2.3 shows the ground-state hyperfine structure (GS-HFS) of a hydrogen atom and its Zeeman splitting in magnetic field [63, 64]. The ground state of the hydrogen atom will split through IJ-coupling as $\Delta E \sim F(F+1) - I(I+1) - J(J+1)$, where I is the proton spin, J is the electron spin and F is the total angular momentum, $\vec{F} = \vec{I} + \vec{J}$. At zero magnetic field, the energy gap between the triplet state ($F = 1$) and the singlet state ($F = 0$) is ΔW . These GS-HFS will further split in a magnet field of 2.5 T through the Zeeman effect. In the beginning, there is a large positive magnetic field, and the electron-spin polarized hydrogen atoms with $m_J = +1/2$ are at states ① and ②. Then the magnetic field is adiabatically turned down to $\sim +1$ G. During this process, the states of hydrogen atoms will follow the line in Fig. 2.3. Next, the magnetic field is rapidly jumped from $\sim +1$ G to ~ -1 G and this leads the states of hydrogen atoms jumping to the state on the line labeled ④. Finally, the magnetic field is adiabatically turned up to a large negative value and the states of hydrogen atoms follow the ④ line. This makes the electron-spin polarized hydrogen atoms transform to proton-spin polarized atoms, which will then pass through a Na-jet ionized cell to become H^- ions and be accelerated to 35 keV. The OPPIS produces 500 μA in a single 300 μs pulse, which corresponds to 9×10^{11} polarized H^- .

2.3 Siberian Snakes

The orbital motion of the proton in an external magnetic field in the lab frame follows the Lorentz force equation:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{v}}{dt} = - \left(\frac{e}{\gamma M} \right) \mathbf{B}_\perp \times \mathbf{v}, \quad (2.1)$$

where $\gamma = E/M$ with E and M are proton energy and mass, respectively. In contrast, the spin precession of the proton in an external magnetic field

Figure 2.3: Breit-Rabi diagram of GS-HFS of hydrogen atom with Zeeman splitting in magnetic field. Sona transition happens when magnetic field rapidly jumps from $\sim +1$ G to ~ -1 G.

in the lab frame follows the Thomas-BMT equation [65]

$$\frac{d\mathbf{S}}{dt} = - \left(\frac{e}{\gamma M} \right) [(1 + G\gamma)\mathbf{B}_\perp + (1 + G)\mathbf{B}_\parallel] \times \mathbf{S}, \quad (2.2)$$

where \mathbf{S} is the proton spin and $G = 1.7928$ is the anomalous magnetic moment of the proton. The number of full spin precessions $G\gamma$ (in the moving frame of proton) for every full revolution is called the spin tune ν_{sp} .

In Fig. 2.4, the vertical magnetic field B_x makes the spin precession around the x-axis. In the moving frame of the proton, the spin will rotate an angle of $G\gamma\theta$, if the proton has an orbital motion of angle θ . Supposing the depolarizing effects lead to a magnetic field in the y direction B_y and depolarization by an angle

$$d\alpha = \omega dt = \frac{e}{\gamma M} (1 + G\gamma) B_y \cos(G\gamma\theta) \frac{ds}{v} \approx \frac{Ge}{Mc} B_y \cos(G\gamma\theta) ds, \quad (2.3)$$

where $\omega = \frac{e}{\gamma M} (1 + G\gamma) B_y$, from Eq. 2.2. ds is the position displacement of the proton and its velocity is approximated to the speed of light. The

Figure 2.4: Spin precession and depolarization.

strength of depolarizing resonances is the average change of the depolarizing angle per radian of the orbit angle

$$\epsilon = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{\theta=0}^{2\pi} d\alpha \approx \frac{Ge}{2\pi Mc} \int B_y \cos(G\gamma\theta) ds, \quad (2.4)$$

where the integral is over a complete revolution around the accelerator. For the imperfection resonances, which are driven by magnetic errors and misalignments, the field B_y is function of the location of the magnets and has periodicity for $\theta \rightarrow \theta + 2\pi$. As a result,

$$B_y = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{yn}^0 \cos(n\theta + \phi_n) \quad (2.5)$$

and the resonances occur when the spin tune $\nu_{sp} = G\gamma = n$ is an integer. For the intrinsic resonance, which are driven by focusing fields, the field B_y is coming from the vertical betatron oscillations traversing the intrinsic machine filed gradients

$$B_y = \frac{dB_y}{dx} \Delta x = \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_{ynP}^{\prime 0} \cos(nP\theta + \phi_{nP}) \right) \Delta x^0 \cos(\nu_x\theta + \varphi), \quad (2.6)$$

where P is the superperiodicity of the focusing field and ν_x is vertical betatron tune. The resonances occur when $\nu_{sp} = G\gamma = nP \pm \nu_x$. For the imperfection-intrinsic “beat” resonances, the field B_y is coming from the imperfection driven vertical betatron oscillations traversing the intrinsic machine field gradients [66]

$$B_y = \frac{dB_y}{dx} \Delta x = \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B'_{ynP} \cos(nP\theta + \phi_{nP}) \right) \left(\sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \Delta x_l^0 \cos(l\theta + \varphi_l) \right). \quad (2.7)$$

The resonances occur when $\nu_{sp} = G\gamma = nP \pm l$. The depolarizing resonances will change the polarization of accelerated beam as [67]

$$\frac{P_f}{P_i} = 2 \exp\left(-\frac{\pi\epsilon^2}{2\Gamma}\right) - 1, \quad (2.8)$$

where P_i and P_f are the polarizations before and after the resonance crossing, respectively, ϵ is defined in Eq. 2.4, and $\Gamma = \frac{d}{d\theta}(G\gamma)$ for imperfection resonances or $\frac{d}{d\theta}(G\gamma \mp \nu_x)$ for intrinsic resonances is the rate at which the resonance is adiabatically crossed during beam acceleration, in unit of radian of the orbit angle [68]. When the beam is slowly accelerated ($\Gamma \ll \epsilon^2$) through the resonance, the spin vector will adiabatically follow the stable spin direction resulting in spin flip. However, for a faster acceleration rate partial depolarization or partial spin flip will occur.

To reduce the depolarizing resonances, RHIC uses two Siberian Snakes (see Fig. 2.1) and each rotates the proton spin by 180° around an axis lying in the horizontal plane [69, 70]. Each Snake is composed of helical dipole magnet with field

$$\begin{aligned} B_x &= B_0 \cos(kz + \phi), & B_y &= B_0 \sin(kz + \phi), \\ B_z &= 0, & 0 &\leq \phi < \pi, \end{aligned} \quad (2.9)$$

where $|k| = 2\pi/\lambda$ with period λ and $h = k/|k|$ is the helicity of helical magnet. The particle trajectory can be solved by equation of motion in magnetic field assuming $\dot{z} \approx c$

$$\gamma M \ddot{\mathbf{r}} = e \dot{\mathbf{r}} \times \mathbf{B}, \quad (2.10)$$

which gives the orbital coordinates (x, y) and angles $(x' = \frac{dx}{dz}, y' = \frac{dy}{dz})$ after

one helical period

$$\begin{aligned} x &= x_0 + x'_0 \lambda - \frac{K}{\gamma} h \lambda \cos \phi, & x' &= x'_0, \\ y &= y_0 + y'_0 \lambda - \frac{K}{\gamma} h \lambda \sin \phi, & y' &= y'_0, \end{aligned} \quad (2.11)$$

where x_0, y_0 (x'_0, y'_0) are initial coordinates (angles) at the entrance of the magnet. Here

$$K = \frac{eB_0}{Mc|k|} \quad (2.12)$$

is generally used for describing the properties of undulator radiation. The spin rotation under helical magnetic field can be solved by using a rotating frame coincident with the magnetic field. After one helical period, the spin will rotate around

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + A^2 K^2}} [AK(\hat{\mathbf{e}}_x \cos \phi + \hat{\mathbf{e}}_y \sin \phi) + h\hat{\mathbf{e}}_z] \quad (2.13)$$

with an angle $\kappa = 2\pi\sqrt{1 + A^2 K^2}$. Here $A = G + 1/\gamma$. For sufficient large energy $\gamma \rightarrow \infty$, the spin rotation is independent of particle energy. A spinor χ in the $\mathbf{2}$ representation of SU(2) group rotates after one helical period

$$\chi \rightarrow \exp\left(\frac{-i\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}\kappa}{2}\right) \chi, \quad (2.14)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ are Pauli matrices.

From Eq. 2.11 and Eq. 2.14, the 180° spin rotation (full Snake) around arbitrary horizontal axis without net orbit excursion can be achieved by four helical dipole magnets, each with N_i periods and the symmetry conditions

1. $h_1 = h_4, h_2 = h_3,$
2. $K_1 = -K_4, K_2 = -K_3,$ the sign comes from B_0 in Eq. 2.12.
3. $N_1 = N_4, N_2 = N_3,$
4. The magnetic field at the entrance of each magnet is in the vertical direction, x-axis in Fig. 2.4, with $\phi = 0$ in Eq. 2.11, such that the orbital excursion is canceled.

Figure 2.5: Design of the Siberian Snake.

To balance the orbit excursion and magnetic field integral, RHIC uses $N_1 = N_2 = 1$, as shown in Fig. 2.5. The + sign denotes the helicity, which is the same for all magnets. The magnets are capable of producing a central field of up to 4 T which spirals through 360° over a length of approximately 2.4 m.

The rotation axis of the two Snakes, say y-axis and z-axis in Fig. 2.4, are perpendicular to each other. The two rotations per revolution through the two full Snakes effectively result in 180° spin precession around the stable vertical direction, x-axis in Fig. 2.4. Consequently, the spin tune becomes $\nu_{sp} = \frac{1}{2}$ and is independent of the beam energy. As a result, the conditions for imperfection resonances with $\nu_{sp} = n$ and intrinsic resonances with $\nu_{sp} = nP + \nu_x$ cannot be satisfied as long as the vertical betatron tune $\nu_x \neq \frac{1}{2}$.

2.3.1 Spin Rotators

The purpose of the Spin Rotators is to provide the longitudinal spin polarization before collisions at RHIC interaction points (IP). Similar to Siberian Snakes, the Spin Rotators are helical dipole magnets to rotate the spin from the vertical direction to the horizontal plane. Then the bending magnets will further rotate the spin to the longitudinal direction. The restoration of particle orbit after the Rotator implies (see Eq. 2.11)

$$\sum_{i=1}^4 K_i h_i \cos \phi_i = 0, \quad \sum_{i=1}^4 K_i h_i \sin \phi_i = 0. \quad (2.15)$$

RHIC uses the design shown in Fig. 2.6 to achieve zero net orbit excursion. The magnetic field at the entrance of each magnet is in the horizontal direc-

Figure 2.6: Design of the Spin Rotator.

tion, y-axis in Fig. 2.4.

2.4 Acceleration System

2.4.1 LINAC

After OPPIS, the proton-spin polarized H^- ions are accelerated from 35 keV to 200 MeV with a radio-frequency quadrupole (RFQ) and the 200 MHz Linear Accelerator (LINAC) with an efficiency of about 50%. At the end of LINAC, the H^- ions are stripped of their electrons and become polarized protons.

2.4.2 Booster

The polarized protons from the LINAC are injected into the Booster, which is a fast cycling synchrotron. It accelerates the protons to 1.5 GeV kinetic energy. A 300 μs pulse of protons are captured into a single bunch, which contains about 4×10^{11} protons. The two weak imperfection-intrinsic “beat” resonances (Eq. 2.7) at $\nu_{sp} = 3$ and 4 are easily corrected by a harmonic correction that cancels the third and fourth harmonic components of the imperfection driven vertical closed orbit distortion [71] since there are only two of them.

2.4.3 AGS

After the Booster, the protons are injected into the Alternating Gradient Synchrotron (AGS) and further accelerated to 25 GeV. The imperfection resonances (Eq. 2.5) are overcome by a 5% (9° rotation around the beam direction) and a 15% partial Snakes, the latter was installed in 2005 [72]. Due to space limitations, full Snake cannot be installed. Weak intrinsic resonances are overcome by a fast tune jump with the partial Snakes, which effectively makes the Γ in Eq. 2.8 large. Strong intrinsic resonances (Eq. 2.6) happen at $G\gamma = 0 + \nu_x$, $12 + \nu_x$, $36 - \nu_x$ and $36 + \nu_x$, since the AGS has superperiodicity $P = 12$ and $\nu_x \approx 8.8$. They are overcome by an RF dipole with the spin resonance location $n \pm \nu_m$ near the intrinsic spin resonance, where ν_m is the modulation tune [73, 74]. The spin near the intrinsic resonance will adiabatically follow the spin closed orbit of the RF spin resonance and result in a full spin-flip, such that the depolarizing effects are canceled.

2.4.4 RHIC

The protons from AGS are transferred to the RHIC through the AGS to RHIC transfer line (AtR) and further accelerated to $\sqrt{s} = 62.4, 200, 500$ or 510 GeV. The AtR has an efficiency of 50% that results in 2×10^{11} protons in each bunch. There are two rings on RHIC: the Blue ring rotates clockwise and the Yellow ring rotates counterclockwise. The depolarizing resonances are overcome by two Siberian Snakes (Sec. 2.3). The spin polarization is monitored by proton-Carbon (pC) polarimeters (Sec. 2.5). To provide longitudinal spin polarization, the vertical spin is rotated to the longitudinal direction before collision (Sec. 2.3.1). There are 360 buckets and every third of them is available to fill. 111 of the 120 crossings are filled with a bunch of protons and the remaining 9 crossings (referred to as “abort gap”) are left empty for beam dumping. The interval of each crossing is 106 ns.

2.5 Polarimeters

The proton spin polarization is monitored by a proton-Carbon (pC) polarimeter, which is calibrated by a Hydrogen-jet (H-jet) polarimeter. The beam polarization is determined by the left and right scattering asymmetry

$$P = \frac{1}{A_N} \frac{N_L - N_R}{N_L + N_R}, \quad (2.16)$$

where P is the beam polarization, N_L and N_R are the number of scatters left and right normalized by luminosity, A_N is the transverse single spin asymmetry and can be known from experiment or theory. One approximation to calculate the analyzing power A_N is by the Coulomb-Nuclear Interference (CNI) [75]. Rather than using a Hamiltonian that adds the electromagnetic and hadronic Hamiltonians together, the CNI assumes the scattering amplitude T , which is related to the scattering matrix $S = 1 + iT$, can be expressed in Fig. 2.7, with T_{em} approximated in Fig. 2.8, in the small angle and high energy region. From CNI, the analyzing power is calculated as

$$A_N(-t) = \frac{Gt_0(-t)\sqrt{-t}}{M(t^2 + t_0^2)}, \quad (2.17)$$

where G is the anomalous magnetic moment of the proton, M is the proton mass, t is the square of the four momentum transferred, and $t_0 = 8\pi\alpha Z/\sigma_{tot}$. The total cross section σ_{tot} is only weakly dependent on energy in the RHIC energy range. For the hydron target in H-jet polarimeter, $Z = 1$ and $\sigma_{tot} = 35$ mb. For the carbon target in pC polarimeter, $Z = 6$ and $\sigma_{tot} = 330$ mb. The analyzing power A_N from elastic scattering in the small angle CNI region with $-t$ from 0.002 to 0.01 GeV² is about 3–5% in the RHIC energy range from 24–250 GeV. Its $-t$ dependence is shown in Fig. 2.9.

The pC polarimeter is located at 12 o'clock position on the RHIC ring (Fig. 2.10a). The schematic view of pC collisions is shown in Fig. 2.10c. There are six Silicon detectors located around the carbon target with a radius of 15 cm. To confirm the polarization is in the correct direction, the six Silicon detectors are combined differently to produce various asymmetries (Fig. 2.10b). If the spin is polarized in the vertical direction, then there will be asymmetries between detector 5 and 2, as well as combined detectors 6+4 and 1+3, but the false asymmetries are shown in the lower part of Fig. 2.10b should be zero.

The analyzing power A_N can be measured by the H-jet polarimeter and used to calibrate the pC polarimeter [76, 77]. In Fig. 2.11, the RHIC proton beam elastically scatters from a vertically polarized atomic hydrogen target. The displacement of two RHIC beams is about 10 mm and only the clockwise beam interacts with the H-jet target. A set of Helmholtz coils are located around the interaction point to provide a uniform vertical magnetic holding field (0.12 T). In the covered $-t$ range from 0.001 to 0.032 GeV², the scattered beam protons do not exit the beam pipe and only the recoil particles from the H-jet target are measured. Due to the low momentum of the recoiled

Figure 2.7: Relationship between the electromagnetic (T_{em}), pure nuclear (T_n) and complete (T) amplitudes in the CNI approximation. Lines marked by || are on the mass shell.

Figure 2.8: Expansion of the complete electromagnetic amplitude T_{em} in powers of fine structure constant α . Lines marked by || are on the mass shell.

Figure 2.9: Analyzing power A_N from CNI for pp and pC scattering.

particles, second coaxial Helmholtz coils with opposite circulating currents are installed to cancel the deflection of the recoil proton trajectory. With a near-zero magnetic field integral $\int Bdl$, the trajectory deviation is less than 3 mm for the lowest momentum proton, and the left and right acceptances are almost identical. The polarized H-jet target is produced from an atomic hydrogen source under a radio frequency (RF) discharge. Two RF transitions flip the nuclear spin of the H-jet target, of which one or the other is turned on every 600 s to reverse the proton spin with efficiency above 99%. The net proton polarization is measured by a Breit-Rabi polarimeter located below the interaction point and turned out to be 0.924 ± 0.018 after taking into account a $(3.5 \pm 2.0)\%$ contamination molecules bounded by hydrogen atoms. The H-jet target has beam intensity of 1.2×10^{17} H atoms/s with a speed of 1560 ± 50 m/s. The analyzing power is measured as

$$A_N = -\frac{1}{P_T} \frac{\sqrt{N_L^\uparrow \cdot N_R^\downarrow} - \sqrt{N_R^\uparrow \cdot N_L^\downarrow}}{\sqrt{N_L^\uparrow \cdot N_R^\downarrow} + \sqrt{N_R^\uparrow \cdot N_L^\downarrow}}, \quad (2.18)$$

where $N_{L(R)}^{\uparrow(\downarrow)}$ is the number of selected pp elastic scattering events, L (R) denotes the left (right) scattering and \uparrow (\downarrow) denotes the target polarization, P_T is the H-jet target polarization discussed above.

(a) pC polarimeter at RHIC 12 o'clock interaction point.

(b) Asymmetries from different detector combinations.

(c) Schematic graph of pC collisions. Beam is going into the paper in the left graph. The carbon target is $5.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ thick and $11.6 \mu\text{m}$ wide.

Figure 2.10: RHIC pC polarimeter.

Figure 2.11: Schematic layout of the H-jet polarimeter.

2.6 Spin Patterns

There are 120 crossings on the RHIC ring, of which 111 are filled with bunches of particles. For the 2013 run of RHIC (run 13), the collision particles are longitudinally polarized protons. The sequence of the beam polarization directions is called the spin pattern. One example of spin patterns is shown in Fig. 2.12. We classify the spin patterns by the starting sequence of the same ($++$ or $--$ and marked by “S”) or the opposite ($+-$ or $-+$ and marked by “O”) spin polarizations between the Blue and Yellow beams. For example, the spin pattern shown in Fig. 2.12 is classified as SSOO. Run 13 has four different types of spin patterns: SOOSSOO, OSSSOSS, SSOO, OOSS. The first two types of spin patterns are used for the first two weeks of run 13, while the last two types are used for the remainder period. The purpose of using interleaved spin polarizations is to reduce the difference of luminosity and efficiencies between collisions with same and opposite helicities, where the difference comes from fluctuations during the run. Since different electric circuits with different efficiencies in the EMCal (Sec. 3.3) are used for even and odd crossings, spin measurements are usually separated for even and odd crossings. For run 13, four types of spin patterns separated for even and odd crossings lead to eight groups of data in the spin measurements.

Figure 2.12: Example spin pattern of run 13. Red and green are even and odd crossings, respectively. This example is classified as SSOO type of spin patterns.

The longitudinal double-spin asymmetry from the measurement is

$$A_{LL} = \frac{\Delta\sigma}{\sigma} = \frac{\sigma_{++} + \sigma_{--} - \sigma_{+-} - \sigma_{-+}}{\sigma_{++} + \sigma_{--} + \sigma_{+-} + \sigma_{-+}}, \quad (2.19)$$

where σ_{++} (σ_{+-}) is the cross section for the same (opposite) helicity proton collisions. Systematic uncertainties between different spin polarizations are largely reduced due to the rapid changing of the spin polarization direction at RHIC. This is not true for the polarized DIS in fixed-target experiments, where the target spin polarization is reversed only after several hours.

2.7 RHIC Performance

For the longitudinal polarized proton beams, one of the interesting physical quantities to measure is the longitudinal double spin asymmetry A_{LL} defined in Sec. 5.1, of which the statistical uncertainty is roughly inversely proportional to $\langle P \rangle^2 \cdot \sqrt{\mathcal{L}}$, where $\langle P \rangle$ is the average beam polarization and \mathcal{L} is the integrated luminosity. We can define the figure of merit (FoM) for the statistical uncertainty as

$$\text{FoM} = \langle P \rangle^2 \cdot \sqrt{\mathcal{L}}. \quad (2.20)$$

Tab. 2.1 lists the average polarization ($\langle P \rangle$), integrated luminosity (\mathcal{L}) and figure of merit ($\langle P \rangle^2 \cdot \sqrt{\mathcal{L}}$) for the longitudinally polarized RHIC runs with $\sqrt{s} = 200, 500$ and 510 GeV. Run 13 has much larger FoM than previous runs and finally fulfills the statistical requirements for the “golden” measurement of direct photon A_{LL} , which is predicted three decades ago [78, 79].

Year	\sqrt{s} (GeV)	$\langle P \rangle$	\mathcal{L} (pb ⁻¹)	FoM (pb ^{-1/2})
2003	200	0.34	0.35	0.068
2005	200	0.47	3.4	0.407
2006	200	0.55	7.5	0.828
2009	200	0.56	16	1.254
2009	500	0.34	14	0.432
2011	500	0.48	18	0.977
2012	510	0.52	32	1.529
2013	510	0.53	155	3.497

Table 2.1: Average polarization ($\langle P \rangle$), integrated luminosity (\mathcal{L}) and figure of merit ($\langle P \rangle^2 \cdot \sqrt{\mathcal{L}}$) for the longitudinally polarized RHIC runs with $\sqrt{s} = 200, 500$ and 510 GeV.

Chapter 3

PHENIX Detector

3.1 Detector Overview

The PHENIX detector [80] is designed to study nuclear matter under extreme conditions through various heavy ion collisions, as well as the proton spin structure through polarized proton collisions. PHENIX is capable to measure electron and muon pairs, photons, and hadrons with excellent energy and momentum resolution. The cutaway drawing of the PHENIX detector is shown in Fig. 3.1. Its beam and side view are shown in Fig. 3.2. The PHENIX magnet system [81] consists of Central Magnet (CM) and Muon Magnet North (MMN) and South (MMS). CM has axial field configuration and $|\eta| < 0.35$ coverage. MMN and MMS have radial field configuration and covers $1.1 < \eta < 2.4$ and $-2.2 < \eta < -1.1$, respectively. The cutaway drawing and field view of the PHENIX magnets are shown in Fig. 3.3.

3.2 Global Detectors

The global detectors [82] used in the direct photon measurement in $\vec{p} + \vec{p}$ collisions include Beam-Beam Counters (BBC) and Zero-Degree Calorimeters (ZDC).

3.2.1 BBC

The purpose of BBC is to measure the time and vertex position of beam-beam collisions, as well as to produce a signal for the PHENIX Level 1

Figure 3.1: Cutaway drawing of the PHENIX detector.

Figure 3.2: Beam and side view of PHENIX detector.

Figure 3.3: The PHENIX magnets.

(LVL1) trigger. The BBC consists of two detectors on the North (BBCN) and South (BBCS) side of the collision point along the beam axis. BBCN and BBCS are located at ± 144 cm (just behind the central magnet) from the center of the interaction region and surround the beam pipe. They cover the $|\eta|$ range from 3.0 to 3.9 over full azimuthal angle. The BBC is made of 64 mesh-dynode photomultiplier (PMT) tubes with 25.4 mm diameter, of which each is mounted on a 30 mm long quartz Cherenkov radiator, as shown in Fig. 3.4a. Fig. 3.4b shows the BBC array comprising of 64 tubes with 30 (10) cm outer (inner) diameter. Fig. 3.4c shows the schematic drawing of 64 BBC channels. The event start time t_0 is determined by the average arriving time of the leading charge particles at BBCN (t_N) and BBCS (t_S)

$$t_0 = \frac{t_N + t_S}{2} - \frac{L}{c}, \quad (3.1)$$

where $L = 144$ cm is the distance between the center of the interaction region and BBC and c is the speed of light. The distance between the collision vertex and the center of the interaction region can be calculated as

$$z_{vtx} = c \times \frac{t_N - t_S}{2}. \quad (3.2)$$

(a) Single BBC tube consisting of mesh-dynode PMT tubes with 25.4 mm diameter mounted on a 30 mm long quartz Cherenkov radiator. (b) BBC array comprising 64 tubes.

(c) Schematic drawing of 64 BBC channels.

Figure 3.4: Design of BBC.

Figure 3.5: Side view of ZDC.

3.2.2 ZDC

ZDCs are hadronic calorimeters located at ± 18 m from the interaction point at both north and south side of the interaction region [83]. ZDC is designed to measure the evaporation neutrons produced during the collisions in a very narrow cone around the beam with $\theta < 2$ mrad (Fig. 3.5). The ZDCs can be used together with BBCs for event selections.

The ZDC consists of three modules along the beam direction as shown in the left of Fig. 3.6. One of the modules is shown in the right of Fig. 3.6. Each module is 100×136 mm² in the transverse direction as shown in the right of Fig. 3.7. It consists of 27 layers of 5 mm Tungsten alloy plates as the absorber, which uses the PMMA based optical fibers to produce Cherenkov light and the PMT at the end to collect the signal. Each module has $1.7 \lambda_I$ (nuclear interaction length) and $\sim 50 X_0$ (radiation length).

3.3 EMCal

The Electromagnetic Calorimeter (EMCal) [84] is designed to detect electromagnetic showers from photons and electrons. It also provides the ability to do hadron PID. The EMCal is located ~ 5 m away from the interaction point at midrapidity with pseudorapidity $|\eta| < 0.35$ and π coverage in azimuthal angle. The EMCal is composed of eight sectors: six sectors are Lead-Scintillator (PbSc) calorimeters and two sectors are Lead-Glass (PbGl) calorimeters. The West Arm has four PbSc, while the East Arm has two PbSc and two PbGl, as shown in Fig. 3.2. The PbSc is better at linearity

Figure 3.6: Left: three ZDC modules. Right: one ZDC module. The beam direction is marked by the red arrow.

and timing and its response to hadrons is better understood. The PbGl has finer granularity and better energy resolution. PHENIX intentionally uses different types of EMCAL to provide a cross check for the measurements.

3.3.1 PbSc

The PbSc is a sampling calorimeter, of which the tower is shown in Fig. 3.8a. The electromagnetically interacting particles will interact with the Pb absorber to produce EM showers, which generate flashes in the scintillating material. The produced light is collected by the optical fibers, which are woven through the calorimeter and are taken to PMTs at the back. The lateral segmentation of the tower is $5.535 \times 5.535 \text{ cm}^2$ corresponding to $0.011 \times 0.011 \text{ rad}^2$ when located $\sim 5 \text{ m}$ away. The active depth is 37.5 cm.

Each PbSc module is mechanically grouped by 2×2 towers (Fig. 3.9a). Each PbSc supermodule consists of 6×6 modules. Each PbSc sector is composed of 6×3 supermodules. This grouping style makes it easy to create a building block with a minimum of supporting components.

The energy response of PbSc to electrons, pions and protons is shown in Fig. 3.11. The energy resolution of PbSc (Fig. 3.10a) is

$$\frac{\sigma(E)}{E} = 2.1\% \oplus \frac{8.1\%}{\sqrt{E/GeV}} \quad (3.3)$$

Figure 3.7: Left: side view of the ZDC module (beam direction indicated by the red arrow). Right: front view (along the beam) of the module. Dimensions are in units of mm.

Figure 3.8: Principle of EMCal.

Figure 3.9: Interior view of a EMCal modules.

Figure 3.10: Energy resolution of EMCal.

and the position resolution is

$$\sigma_x(E, \theta) = 1.55\text{mm} \oplus \frac{5.7\text{mm}}{\sqrt{E/\text{GeV}}} \oplus 0.8X_0 \sin \theta, \quad (3.4)$$

where \oplus means sum in quadrature, θ is the impact angle ($\theta = 0$ for orthogonal impact), and X_0 is the radiation length (22 mm for PbSc).

3.3.2 PbGl

The PbGl is a homogeneous calorimeter and collects the Cherenkov radiations produced by charged particles including the e^+e^- pairs created by incoming photons (Fig. 3.8b). PbGl is made from 55% PbO and 45% SiO₂ and has a refraction index $n = 1.648$. The transverse area of PbGl is $4 \times 4 \text{ cm}^2$, which corresponds to $0.008 \times 0.008 \text{ rad}^2$ when located $\sim 5 \text{ m}$ away. Its length is 40 cm and corresponds to $14.4 X_0$, where $X_0 \approx 28 \text{ mm}$ is the radiation length.

6×4 towers are glued together to form a supermodule of PbGl (Fig. 3.9b). Each Front End Module (FEM) reads out 2×3 supermodules. Each sector consists of 16×12 supermodules.

The energy resolution of PbGl (Fig. 3.10b) is

$$\frac{\sigma(E)}{E} = 0.8\% \oplus \frac{5.9\%}{\sqrt{E/\text{GeV}}} \quad (3.5)$$

Figure 3.11: Energy response of PbSc to electrons, pions and protons of 0.5, 1 and 2 GeV kinetic energy.

and the position resolution is

$$\sigma_x(E) = 0.2mm \oplus \frac{8.4mm}{\sqrt{E/GeV}}, \quad (3.6)$$

where \oplus means sum in quadrature.

3.4 Tracking System

3.4.1 VTX

The VTX detector [85] is designed to locate primary and secondary vertices with a precision of several micrometers as well as significantly improve tracking performance in conjunction with other detectors. The design of VTX is shown in Fig. 3.12. In run 13, VTX is only installed on the West Arm. The photons interacting with VTX have some probabilities to convert to e^+e^- pairs.

Figure 3.12: Design of VTX detector. Left: 3D view. Right: beam view

3.4.2 Drift Chambers

The Drift Chamber (DC) is a multi-wire gaseous detector belong to the PHENIX central arm tracking system [86]. As shown in Fig. 3.2 and Fig. 3.13a, the DC is located between 2.08 to 2.48 m from the beam and has 2 m long along the beam direction. Both West and East Arms have a DC and they are the mirror image of each other. Each DC covers 90° in azimuthal angle.

The construction of the DC frame is shown in Fig. 3.13a. Each DC frame is supported by a titanium frame and equally divided into 20 sectors. Each sector covers 4.5° azimuthal angle. The wire layout of each sector is shown in Fig. 3.13b. The X1 and X2 wire cells run in parallel with the beam direction and provide precise measurement in the r - ϕ coordinates. U1, V1, U2, and V2 wires have stereo angles of about 6° relative to the beam direction and provide the ability to measure the z coordinate of the track. Each of X and U, V cells have 12 and 4 anode (sense) wires, respectively. Each sense wire is separated in the center into two halves, which are then read out independently.

(a) DC frame. (b) Left: wire position within one DC sector. Right: top view of wire orientation.

Figure 3.13: DC frame and wire layout.

3.4.3 Pad Chambers

There are three Pad Chambers (PCs) named PC1, PC2, and PC3 located between the DC and the EMCal, where PC2 is only installed on the West Arm (Fig. 3.2 and Fig. 3.14). They are multiwire proportional chambers, which measure the positions of charged particles from the drift time of ionized gaseous molecules to the wires. PC1 measures the z coordinate after the DC and gives the direction of the track outside the magnetic field together with the DC information. PC1 is important to determine the three momenta of the charged particles. The information from PC2 and PC3 can be used to resolve the ambiguities in the outer detector since $\sim 30\%$ of the particles hitting the EMCal are produced by either secondary interactions or particle decays outside DC and PC1.

3.4.4 Track Finding in DC

Hits in the DC from a sample track are shown as small circles in Fig. 3.13a. Here ϕ is the polar angle at the intersection of the track with a “reference radius” near the midpoint of the drift chamber, and α is the inclination of the

Figure 3.14: Schematic view of PC1, PC2 and PC3 in the central arm.

track at that point. Since the magnetic field is near zero in and after the DC, the tracks in the DC are almost straight lines. Due to the bending magnetic before DC, $\alpha \propto 1/p_T$. ϕ and α characterize the location of the tracks: hits on the same track have similar values of ϕ and α , otherwise do not. Since any two points define a unique line, the combinatorial Hough transformations (CHT) map two points xy -space to the feature space of the line passing through them described by ϕ and α [87, 88]. The distribution of two-point combinations in the feature space described by ϕ and α has a peak with height $n(n - 1)/2$ for each track with n points on it (Fig. 3.16). Since there is no bending magnetic field for the rz -plane, the z coordinate is determined by a straight line projection to the PC1 if there is an unambiguous PC1 hit. UV hits are associated with the track if there are hits within 5 cm of the DC UV wires. The track quality is assigned a binary value $(\text{FEDCBA})_2$ based on the hit information

- A = 1 if the X1 plane is used,
- B = 1 if the X2 plane is used,
- C = 1 if there are hits in the UV plane,
- D = 1 if there are unique hits in the UV plane,

Figure 3.15: A sample track shown in an xy -plane. The X1 and X2 hits in the DC are shown as small circles with an outline of the DC. ϕ and α are the feature space variables.

- $E = 1$ if there are hits in PC1,
- $F = 1$ if there are unique hits in PC1.

3.5 Triggers

The collision rate at RHIC is so high that the data acquisition (DAQ) system is not able to record all the data. The level 1 (LVL1) triggers [89], which include BBC, ZDC, and ERT triggers (Tab. 3.1), are used to provide an online¹ selection for interesting events. The LVL1 system consists of local level 1 (LL1) triggers, which process detector information into reduced bit data, as well as global level 1 (GL1) triggers, which make trigger decisions and check whether DAQ is busy². Among the GL1 triggers, GL1-1P is designed to store the luminosity information for each bunch crossing and used in spin measurements in polarized proton collisions.

¹Online means during data taking.

²DAQ is busy if it is not able to take data.

Figure 3.16: Hits in the DC (left) and corresponding Hough transformations (right).

BBCLL1	A coincidence of signals from BBCN and BBCS with a threshold set on the number of BBC tubes.
ZDCCLL1	A coincidence of signals from ZDCN and ZDCS with a threshold set on the number of ZDC tubes.
ERTLL1_4x4a	Energy deposit larger than 4.7 (3.7) GeV in 4×4 towers of PbSc (PbGl).
ERTLL1_4x4b	Energy deposit larger than 5.6 (4.7) GeV in 4×4 towers of PbSc (PbGl).
ERTLL1_4x4c	Energy deposit larger than 3.7 (3.7) GeV in 4×4 towers of PbSc (PbGl).

Table 3.1: Definitions of triggers at PHENIX used in RHIC run 13.

3.5.1 Raw, Live and Scaled Triggers

Fig. 3.17 shows the information of BBCLL1, ZDCLL1 and EMCAL (ERTLL1) triggers from a particular run with runnumber = 392548. There are three kinds of trigger count: raw, live, and scaled. The raw count is how many times the trigger is fired. Live count not only requires the trigger to be fired but also requires DAQ is not busy and able to take data. But the data taking does not happen as many times as the live trigger count, since there is not enough disk space to record so much data. Instead, n data are skipped after each recording. The resultant trigger count is the scaled count with scaled down = n . For example, ERT_4x4c&BBCLL1(noVtx) has scale down = 1 in Fig. 3.17, which means if its live trigger is fired four times, it will only take the first and third data. Scale down = 0 means every time the live trigger is fired, the data will be recorded.

3.5.2 Minimum Bias Trigger and Integrated Luminosity

In Fig. 3.18, the probability of a certain particle from blue beam interacting with a certain particle in yellow beam to produce a certain kind of event is

$$P = \frac{\sigma}{A}. \quad (3.7)$$

Since there are $N_B N_Y$ possible combinations in each bunch collision, the average number of events in k_b bunch collisions is

$$N = k_b N_B N_Y \cdot \frac{\sigma}{A}. \quad (3.8)$$

If we define the integrated luminosity as

$$\mathcal{L} \equiv \frac{k_b N_B N_Y}{A}, \quad (3.9)$$

then the event cross section is

$$\sigma = \frac{N}{\mathcal{L}}. \quad (3.10)$$

This means if we want to measure a certain kind of event cross section σ , we need to know not only the number of events N , but also the integrated

Trigger

Note: L1 Trigger Scaler Entries in pink indicate an approximate count due to the fact that Run Control may have crashed and the run was not ended properly.
 select * from trigger where runnumber = 392548 order by bitmb

Name	Bit Mask	Scale Down	State	Raw Trigger Count	Raw Trigger Rate	Live Trigger Count	Live Trigger Rate	Scaled Trigger Count	Scaled Trigger Rate	Lifetime
BBCLL1(>0 tubes)	0x00000001	31141	Enabled	8745354585	1642011.75	8032543155	1508175.58	257933	48.43	0.92
BBCLL1(>0 tubes) novertex	0x00000002	6732	Enabled	14438675030	2710979.16	13263963189	2490417.42	1969993	369.88	0.92
ZDCLL1wide	0x00000004	6227	Enabled	1617869114	303768.14	1495142601	280725.23	240068	45.07	0.92
BBCLL1(noVtx)&(ZDCN ZDCS)	0x00000008	6396	Enabled	6580905721	1235618.80	6080495678	1141662.73	950523	178.47	0.92
BBCLL1(>0 tubes) narrowvtx	0x00000010	4070	Enabled	4215863447	791562.80	3872086615	727015.89	951139	178.58	0.92
ZDCNS	0x00000020	4411	Enabled	1096951505	205961.60	1006403083	188960.40	228106	42.83	0.92
ERT_4x4b	0x00000040	0	Enabled	591258	111.01	535155	100.48	535155	100.48	0.91
ERTLL1_4x4a&BBCLL1(noVtx)	0x00000080	0	Enabled	3672386	689.52	3369752	632.70	3369752	632.70	0.92
ERT_4x4c&BBCLL1(noVtx)	0x00000100	1	Enabled	11046812	2074.13	10206344	1916.32	5103172	958.16	0.92
SG3&MUID_IH_N S	0x00000200	95	Enabled	48406312	9088.68	44220593	8302.78	460631	86.49	0.91
ERTLL1_E&BBCLL1(narrow)	0x00000400	0	Enabled	4234416	795.05	3913981	734.88	3913981	734.88	0.92
CLOCK	0x00000800	46765	Enabled	50037096071	9394873.46	46003099421	8637457.65	983687	184.70	0.92

Figure 3.17: Trigger information from RHIC run 13 with runnumber = 392548.

Figure 3.18: N_B particles from one bunch of blue beam collide with N_Y particles from one bunch of yellow beam with beam overlapping area A . The event cross section is σ .

luminosity \mathcal{L} . At PHENIX, we use Vernier scan technique [90,91] to measure the beam overlapping area A in Eq. 3.9. To calculate integrated luminosity in the future, notice that

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{N}{\sigma} \quad (3.11)$$

is the same for any kind of event. If we can get a “reference” event cross section σ_{ref} and its event count N_{ref} , we can calculate the integrated luminosity as

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{N_{ref}}{\sigma_{ref}}. \quad (3.12)$$

At PHENIX, we use an event that triggers the BBCLL1 as such a “reference” event and measures its cross section σ_{BBC} by Vernier scan. Since σ_{BBC} is a quantity only depending on beam energy and BBCLL1 trigger efficiency, the same value can be used even for different RHIC runs if energy and BBCLL1 efficiency are the same (Of course, the colliding particles should be the same, e.g., pp, pA or AA). Then the corresponding luminosity for any event can be calculated by the corresponding BBCLL1 count N_{BBC} as

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{N_{BBC}}{\sigma_{BBC}}. \quad (3.13)$$

Similar to BBCLL1, ZDCLL1 is also a minimum bias trigger and can be used to measure luminosity. ZDCLL1 is triggered if there is a coincidence of signals from ZDCN and ZDCS, with a threshold set on the deposited energy.

3.5.3 STAR Scaler

PHENIX has three STAR Scaler boards named Ping, Pong, and Pung. They are called STAR Scalers because they were initially designed for use in STAR

Scaler Pin	Ping Trigger	Pong Trigger	Pung Trigger
0	BeamX_0	BeamX_0	MPCN_C_5
1	BeamX_1	BeamX_1	MPCN_C_4
2	BeamX_2	BeamX_2	MPCN_C_3
3	BeamX_3	BeamX_3	MPCN_C_2
4	BeamX_4	BeamX_4	MPCN_C_1
5	BeamX_5	BeamX_5	MPCN_C_0
6	BeamX_6	BeamX_6	ZDC_Wide
7	PARTITION 1 BUSY	PARTITION 1 BUSY	MPC_N_S_B
8	PARTITION 1 ACCEPT	SMD_S_L	BBCnovtx
9	ERT_2x2W	SMD_S_R	BeamX_0
10	ERT_2x2E	SMD_S_U	BeamX_1
11	ZDCNS	SMD_S_D	BeamX_2
12	MPC 4x4C South	SMD_S_H_OR_V	BeamX_3
13	MPC 4x4C North	SMD_N_L	BeamX_4
14	ZDCN	SMD_N_R	BeamX_5
15	ZDCS	SMD_N_U	BeamX_6
16	NHIT6 (BBCN>1)	SMD_N_D	PARTITION 1 BUSY
17	NHIT5 (BBCS>1)	SMD_N_H_OR_V	MPC_N_S_A
18	NHIT4 (BBCN>0)	NHIT4	MPCS_C_5
19	NHIT3 (BBCS>0)	NHIT3	MPCS_C_4
20	ZDC_Narrow	ZDC_N	MPCS_C_3
21	ZDC_Wide	ZDC_S	MPCS_C_2
22	BBCLL1_1	ZDC_Wide (GL1)	MPCS_C_1
23	BBCLL1_0	A_INR	MPCS_C_0

Table 3.2: Scaler pins of the STAR Scaler Ping, Pong and Pung boards for run 13.

Collaboration. Each board has 24 pins as shown in Tab. 3.2, 7 of them are used to label the 120 crossings since $2^7 > 120$. Each pin has a 40-bit deep counter. STAR Scaler boards contain crossing-by-crossing information separated for BBCN and BBCS, as well as ZDCN and ZDCS, and are able to calculate the pile-up corrections from a high collision rate.

3.5.4 EMCal Triggers

4×4 towers of EMCal are grouped to provide three types of LL1 triggers, which are called ERTLL1_4x4a/b/c depending on the energy thresholds listed in Tab. 3.1. EMCal triggers are used to select high-energy particles which deposit sufficient energy in the 4×4 towers of EMCal.

Chapter 4

Direct Photon Cross Section Analysis

The direct photon cross section (Sec. 4.17) from measurement is

$$E \frac{d^3\sigma}{dp^3} = \frac{1}{\mathcal{L}} \cdot \frac{1}{2\pi p_T} \cdot \frac{1}{\Delta p_T \Delta y} \cdot \frac{N_{\text{dir}} \cdot r_{\text{pile-up}}}{\epsilon_{\text{BBC}} \epsilon_{\text{ERT}} \epsilon_{\text{acc}}}, \quad (4.1)$$

where N_{dir} is the direct photon yield in the p_T bin Δp_T wide (Sec. 4.7), which is corrected by BBC and ERT trigger efficiencies ϵ_{BBC} (Sec. 4.10), ϵ_{ERT} (Sec. 4.12), detector acceptance (Sec. 4.16) and pile-up correction $r_{\text{pile-up}}$ (Sec. 4.9). $\mathcal{L} = \frac{N_{\text{BBC}}}{\sigma_{\text{BBC}}}$ is the absolute luminosity (see Sec. 3.5.2). $\sigma_{\text{BBC}} = 32.51 \pm 3.01(\text{syst.}) \pm 1.19(\text{stat.})$ mb is measured in vernier scan in run 9 at $\sqrt{s} = 500$ GeV [92]. The corresponding number of MB events N_{BBC} is given in Sec. 4.1.

4.1 Selection of Data Sample and Quality Assurance

This direct photon cross section analysis used the data set of $\sqrt{s} = 510$ GeV proton-proton collisions at PHENIX from RHIC 2013 running period (run 13). The data taking was separated by 1008 intervals, which are called runs, and each interval ranges from ~ 10 min to ~ 90 min. The first step in the analysis is to filter some problematic runs based on some criteria. This procedure is called quality assurance (QA). The QA of this direct photon analysis

is largely based on that of the π^0 analysis [93] since π^0 is the dominant background in direct photon measurements. A number of runs (corresponding to $\sim 10\%$ of the integrated luminosity) were excluded from the analysis due to the following reasons:

- Trigger livetime (last column of Fig. 3.17) is less than 0.5, which may indicate some problems during data taking.
- There is no π^0 statistics either in MinBias or one of the EMCAL triggered (ERTLL1_4x4a/b/c) samples.
- The scaledown of any of the EMCAL triggers is very high, which is likely due to a problem with EMCAL triggers during data taking.
- π^0 statistics were dropped in PbSc at East Arm.
- The number of fired triggers of one or more EMCAL sectors is significantly lower than the average. Even though this can be corrected by trigger rejection power¹ and efficiency, removing those runs can avoid any possibility for additional systematic uncertainties.
- The ratio of π^0 yield in ERTLL1_4x4c triggered sample over the number of MinBias live events is dropped down. Similar to the above one, this can also be corrected by trigger rejection power and efficiency. But removing those runs can avoid any possibility for additional systematic uncertainties.
- π^0 mass in PbSc is 10% lower than the expected value, which means the gains of the detector is 10% lower.
- Since we used DC to veto charged particles in the selection of photon candidates (Sec. 4.6), we studied DC dead map (Sec. 4.4.1) and required most DC regions were in good condition.

Based on the QA, the analyzed data sample was taken from ERTLL1_4x4c scaled trigger for $p_T = 6\text{--}14$ GeV and ERTLL1_4x4b scaled trigger for $p_T = 14\text{--}30$ GeV. Since the former had an average ~ 2 scaledown value and the latter had zero scaledown, the corresponding integrated luminosities were 11 and 33 pb^{-1} , respectively.

¹It is defined as the number of MinBias events corresponding to one triggered event.

4.2 EMCal Calibration

4.2.1 Energy Calibration

Tower-by-tower global energy calibration was done by using the peak positions of reconstructed π^0 mass in the invariant mass plots of their two decay photons for each tower of EMCal [94]. Firstly, the energy of each tower was scaled to make the diphoton peak position to $135 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ when one of the photon clusters was centered on that tower and using core energy E_{core} for clusters produced by photon showers. Then, the new core energy of each cluster was approximated by scaling the total energy of towers in that cluster as $E_{\text{core}}^{\text{new}} = \frac{E_{\text{total}}^{\text{new}}}{E_{\text{total}}^{\text{old}}} \times E_{\text{core}}^{\text{old}}$. After that, a new invariant mass was plotted by using $E_{\text{core}}^{\text{new}}$. Finally, the above procures were repeated until each $E_{\text{core}}^{\text{new}}$ was convergent to $E_{\text{core}}^{\text{old}}$. The towers which failed to be calibrated were excluded from the analysis. There was also an additional run-by-run calibration for each EMCal sector depending on the run-by-run gain shift of EMCal.

4.2.2 ToF Calibration

EMCal can measure the time-of-flight (ToF) of particles. The uncalibrated ToF is the time difference between EMCal and BBC: $\Delta t = t_{\text{EMCal}} - t_{\text{BBC}}$. Before calibration, Δt measured by each tower was not aligned. ToF of the EMCal tower was calibrated to move the ToF peak of photons to $\Delta t = 0$.

4.3 EMCal Warn Map

A portion of EMCal towers was abnormal due to electronic malfunctions. These towers are fired too frequently and called hot towers. They were identified in the π^0 analysis [93]. Firstly, a distribution of the number of hits per tower for different energy ranges at larger than 0.3 GeV was plotted. For each energy bin, towers in which the number of hits was $10 \times \text{RMS}$ (root-mean-square) greater than the average were declared hot. It was done separately for MB and ERTLL1_4x4c scaled trigger samples. Then the list of hot towers obtained for different energy bins from the two data samples was combined in the final list of bad towers. Non-calibrated towers, as well as edge towers (two rows and two columns, which are usually non-calibrated), were also declared bad. Finally, a 3×3 block of towers around any bad tower were

Figure 4.1: EMCAL warn map for PbSc (left) and PbGl (right) used in this analysis. The edge towers are not included here.

excluded from the analysis (clusters that had a maximal deposited tower in any of the masked towers were excluded from the analysis). Fig. 4.1 shows the warn maps used in the analysis (edge towers are not masked on these plots): about 15% (23%) non-edge towers are masked in PbSc (PbGl).

4.4 DC Tracks

4.4.1 DC QA and Dead Map

We used DC to measure the momentum of charged particles in isolation cut (see Sec. 4.5) and veto the the charged particles (see next subsection) in EMCAL. However, some parts of the DC did not function well for some runs. We studied the DC dead areas in a run-by-run basis and marked them by

dead map for each run. These procedures are the same as those in run 6 direct photon analysis (Sec. 4 of [95] and Sec. 5 of [96]). Firstly, we plotted the number of DC tracks per event for each run and excluded the runs that this value is 3σ lower than the average, as shown in Fig. 4.2. Then, for the remaining runs, we marked the hot (hit much more frequently) and dead (hit much less frequently) areas in the α -board distributions for each group¹ of runs (Fig. 4.3). Here $\alpha \propto 1/p_T$ and board is a function of ϕ

$$\begin{aligned} \text{West Arm: board} &= \frac{0.573231 + \phi - 0.0046 \cos(\phi + 0.05721)}{0.01963496}, \\ \text{East Arm: board} &= \frac{3.72402 - \phi + 0.008047 \cos(\phi + 0.87851)}{0.01963496} \end{aligned} \quad (4.2)$$

and directly related to the hardware design of the DC. We further check that after the dead map, PISA simulations [97] agree well with data (Fig. 4.4).

4.4.2 DC Charge Veto

We used DC tracks of quality > 3 (see Sec. 3.4.4) to veto charged particles in EMCal. If the difference between the DC z position (z_{trk}) and the projected EMCal z position (z_{pemc}), $|z_{\text{trk}} - z_{\text{pemc}}|$, and the difference $|\phi_{\text{emc}} - \phi_{\text{pemc}}|$ are both less than 3σ , we will veto this cluster in EMCal, since it is probably a charged particle and not a photon. Fig. 4.5 and Fig. 4.6 show that the $\sigma_{d\phi} \approx 5$ mrad and $\sigma_{dz} \approx 4$ cm, which are the values we used for 3σ veto.

4.5 Isolation Cut

The leading order processes that produce direct photons in pp collisions include quark-gluon Compton scattering $g + q \rightarrow \gamma + q$, quark-antiquark annihilation $q + \bar{q} \rightarrow \gamma + g$, parton fragmentation to photon [98], and quark bremsstrahlung (see Fig. 1.3). By requiring the energy of other particles in a cone around the signal photon less than several percent of the photon energy (Fig. 4.7), we can remove most of the decay and fragmentation photons. We choose $r_{\text{cone}} = 0.5^2$ and energy fraction = 0.1 as run 6 direct photon

¹In the same group, the runs have similar hot and dead areas.

² r_{cone} cannot be too small, or the NLO calculations won't be enough at the next-to-leading order. The isolated cross section from NLO calculations is even larger than that of the inclusive cross section at $r_{\text{cone}} = 0.1$ (see Table 1 of [61]). On the other hand, r_{cone}

Figure 4.2: Number of tracks per event in DC, separated for North (N) or South (S) and West (W) or East (E) sectors. The red line shows the average. The green line is 3σ lower than the average. The runs which are below the green line were excluded.

Figure 4.3: DC α -board for one specific run for runnumebr = 389576.

Figure 4.4: DC z (left, z is along beam direction) and ϕ (right) distributions between data (red line) and PISA simulation (black line).

analysis [99]. The sum of energy inside the cone was done by using EMCal cluster energy for neutral particles and DC track momentum for charged particles: $\sum E_{\text{in cone}} = \sum E_{\text{EMCal}} + \sum p_{\text{DC}} \times c$. There was a charge veto cut to remove charged particles in EMCal and to avoid double counting between EMCal and DC.

4.6 Photon Selection

The criteria for photon clusters are shown in Tab. 4.1. We used the warn map of EMCal from run 13 π^0 cross section analysis [93] (see Sec. 4.3). As for run 6 direct photon analysis [95, 96], we further excluded 10 (12) edge towers of West and East Arm for PbSc (PbGl) as the guard veto when measuring the signal photons. When using photon pairs to reconstruct π^0 background, we only required this guard veto for the signal photon and not for the partner photon. For the EMCal photon shower shape cut, we used the usual `prob_photon` value, which is the p-value corresponding to the χ^2 of the cluster energy deposit comparing to that of a typical photon cluster. `prob_photon` $>$ 0.02 means photon efficiency is 98%, but we calculated its efficiency by using the π^0 yield with and without this cut (Sec. 4.10). We also

cannot be too large either, since PHENIX can only probe $|\eta| < 0.35$. $r_{\text{cone}} = 0.5$ was a good balance between experimental and theoretical requirements.

Figure 4.5: DC and EMCAL dz distributions. The curves are fitted by $\text{gaus}(0)+\text{pol2}(3)$ and $p2$ is the σ_{dz} of the Gaussian.

Figure 4.6: DC and EMCAL $d\phi$ distributions. The curves are fitted by $\text{gaus}(0)+\text{pol2}(3)$ and $p2$ is the $\sigma_{d\phi}$ of the Gaussian.

Figure 4.7: Isolation cut for direct photons from different sources.

used $|ToF| < 10$ ns cut both for signal photons and clusters in an isolation cone. We also used EMCal energy and DC momentum cuts for clusters and tracks, respectively. Further, we required the EMCal trigger bit of the signal clusters. The DC charge veto has been studied at Sec. 4.4.2. For isolated photons, we further required an isolation cut, as described in Sec. 4.5.

4.7 Direct Photon Yield

4.7.1 Inclusive Direct Photon Yield

The inclusive direct photon yield is

$$\begin{aligned}
 N_{\text{dir}} = & \frac{N_{\text{total}}}{\epsilon} - (1 + R + M\epsilon_{\text{conv}}(1 - \epsilon_{\text{conv}})) \frac{N_{\pi^0}}{\epsilon^2} \\
 & - \frac{M(p_T^{2\gamma})P(p_T^{2\gamma})}{2} \frac{N_{\pi^0}(p_T^{2\gamma})}{\epsilon^2} - A'(1 + R_\eta) \frac{N_{\pi^0}}{\epsilon^2}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.3}$$

$\frac{N_{\text{total}}}{\epsilon}$ is the total photon yield corrected by efficiency $\epsilon = \epsilon_{\text{conv}}\epsilon_{\text{prob}}\epsilon_{\text{ToF}}$, which is the combined efficiency of ToF cut, photon_prob cut and photon conversion (Sec. 4.10). $\frac{N_{\pi^0}}{\epsilon^2}$ is π^0 photon yield (see Sec. 4.8) corrected by efficiency. $R\frac{N_{\pi^0}}{\epsilon^2}$ is the yield of π^0 photons which missed their partners. R is called

EMCal warn map veto	hot and dead towers, and 8 towers around them
EMCal guard veto	10 (12) towers of PbSc (PbGl) for each Arm
EMCal photon shape cut	prob_photon > 0.02 for both PbSc and PbGl
EMCal ToF	ToF < 10 ns
EMCal energy	$E_{\min} > 0.3$ GeV
EMCal trigger bit match	
DC charged track veto	3σ matching of DC tracks of quality > 3
Isolation cut	$\sum E_{\text{EMCal}} + \sum p_{\text{DC}} \times c < 0.1E_\gamma$
EMCal warn map veto	only hot and dead towers
EMCal ToF	ToF < 10 ns
EMCal energy	$E_{\min} > 0.3$ GeV
DC charged track momentum	$0.2 \text{ GeV}/c < p < 15 \text{ GeV}/c$

Table 4.1: Cuts for photon clusters. The upper side cuts are for signal photons. The lower side cuts are for EMCal clusters and DC charged tracks in isolation cone.

missing ratio and was calculated by fast MC simulation in Sec. 4.13. Since there is no detector efficiency implemented, we should correct the efficiency before multiplying R . $M\epsilon_{\text{conv}}(1 - \epsilon_{\text{conv}})\frac{N_{\pi^0}}{\epsilon^2}$ is the yield of merged π^0 photons with their partner photons converted, where M is two photons merging rate w.r.t. single photons p_T from fast MC (Sec. 4.14). Since in this case one photon was converted, what we measured were single photons. $\frac{N_{\pi^0}(p_T^{2\gamma})}{\epsilon^2}$ is the π^0 photon yield w.r.t. photon pairs p_T , of which $\frac{M(p_T^{2\gamma})P(p_T^{2\gamma})}{2} \frac{N_{\pi^0}(p_T^{2\gamma})}{\epsilon^2}$ were merged and passed the prob_photon cut. $M(p_T^{2\gamma})$ is two photons merging rate w.r.t. photon pairs p_T from fast MC (Sec. 4.14), since what we measure were photon pairs. $P(p_T^{2\gamma})$ is the ratio of the yield of the merged photon pairs passed the prob_photon cut over the yield of all merged photon pairs calculated from PISA simulations (Sec. 4.14). For photons from other hadrons (η , ω and η'), rather than measured them directly, we used the ratio of their photon yield over that of π^0 photon yield from 200 GeV data, which was denoted by A (Sec. 4.15). $A'(1 + R_\eta)\frac{N_{\pi^0}}{\epsilon^2}$ is the yield of photons from other hadrons' decay, where

$$A' = A \frac{1 + 2R + M}{1 + 2R_\eta}, \quad (4.4)$$

which was corrected from A by different missing ratio of π^0 (R) and η (R_η), and the fact that photon pairs from η do not merge when $p_T < 30 \text{ GeV}/c$.

The statistical uncertainty of N_{dir} was calculated by square root of quadratic sum of variations of each yield:

$$\Delta N_{\text{dir}} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=\text{total},\pi^0} \left(\frac{\partial N_{\text{dir}}}{\partial N_i} \Delta N_i \right)^2}, \quad (4.5)$$

by assuming that yeild of total photons and π^0 's were independent.

4.7.2 Isolated Direct Photon Yield

The isolated direct photon yield is

$$\begin{aligned} n_{\text{dir}} = & \frac{n_{\text{total}}}{\epsilon} - (1 + M\epsilon_{\text{conv}}(1 - \epsilon_{\text{conv}})) \frac{n_{\pi^0}}{\epsilon^2} - R \frac{N_{\pi^0}}{\epsilon^2} \\ & - \frac{M(p_T^{2\gamma})P(p_T^{2\gamma})}{2} \frac{N_{\pi^0}(p_T^{2\gamma})}{\epsilon^2} - A'(V + R_\eta) \frac{N_{\pi^0}}{\epsilon^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.6)$$

This is similar to inclusive direct photon yield, except that we should consider other hadrons self-veto for their decay photons. Here V is η meson self-veto due to isolation cut (Sec. 4.15). In addition, we should consider isolated π^0 yield with and without self-veto as follows:

- n_{π^0} : π^0 photons passed the isolation cut. The partner photon from π^0 gave the self-veto for isolation cut. When we could reconstruct the two clusters from π^0 decay products, we used this n_{π^0} , as in $(1 + M\epsilon_{\text{conv}}(1 - \epsilon_{\text{conv}})) \frac{n_{\pi^0}}{\epsilon^2}$.
- N_{π^0} : π^0 photons passed the isolation cut if their partner photons were removed. $R \frac{N_{\pi^0}}{\epsilon^2}$ is the yield of missed π^0 photons, since missing one photon means no self-veto. $\frac{M(p_T^{2\gamma})P(p_T^{2\gamma})}{2} \frac{N_{\pi^0}(p_T^{2\gamma})}{\epsilon^2}$ is the yield of merged π^0 photons, since merged photons have no self-veto. $A'(V + R_\eta) \frac{N_{\pi^0}}{\epsilon^2}$ is the yield of other hadrons, of which the self-veto was included in V , so we use N_{π^0} here.

The statistical uncertainty Δn_{dir} was calculated similarly as Eq. 4.5.

4.8 π^0 Invariant Mass Tagging

The π^0 was tagged by its invariant mass. We plotted the yield of photon pairs vs their invariant mass m_{inv} for each p_T bin, fit with Gaussian plus 3rd degree polynomial (gaus+pol3) with $0.06 \text{ GeV}/c^2 < m_{\text{inv}} < 0.25 \text{ GeV}/c^2$. The π^0 yield was calculated as the yield of photon pairs in the peak region subtracting background in the peak region from the fitting polynomial, where the peak region was chosen as $0.11 \text{ GeV}/c^2 < m_{\text{inv}} < 0.16 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ for p_T less than $10 \text{ GeV}/c$ and $0.10 \text{ GeV}/c^2 < m_{\text{inv}} < 0.17 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ for p_T larger than $10 \text{ GeV}/c$. For p_T larger than $16 \text{ GeV}/c$, the yield of two-photon pairs was too few to do the fitting. Instead, we used background fraction calculated from fast MC simulations to do background subtraction.

4.9 Pile-up Correction

4.9.1 Inclusive Photon Pile-up Correction

Due to high luminosity, there were chances that several collisions happened in one event. We plotted the yield per event vs the event rate and extracted the yield per event at zero event rate to correct the pile-up effects. By using ERT_4x4c data, the photon yield per event vs the event rate is shown in Fig. 4.8. We fit the photon yield per event vs event rate with a linear function $p0 + p1 * x$ and a log function $-p0 * \log(1 - p1 * x) / (p1 * x)$. The ratio between the fitting constant $p0$ and the average photon yield per event for all runs (i.e., $p0/\text{mean}$) is the pile-up factor and shown in Fig. 4.9. We used the average value of $p0/\text{mean}$ over p_T from log fitting as the central value for the pile-up factor. The difference between log and linear fittings was assigned as systematic uncertainties.

4.9.2 Isolated Photon Pile-up Correction

The pile-up for isolated photons was calculated in the same way. Fig. 4.10 shows isolated photon yield per event vs event rate. $p0/\text{mean}$ vs p_T is shown in Fig. 4.11. We used the average value of $p0/\text{mean}$ over p_T from log fitting as the central value for the pile-up factor. The difference between log and linear fittings was assigned as systematic uncertainties.

Figure 4.8: Photon yield (normalized by ERT_4x4c scaled counts) vs event rate (BBCLL1 narrow live over clock live counts) from ERT_4x4c data sample for $p_T = 6 - 30$ GeV. The upper plots only include shower profile cut; the lower plots include both shower profile and ToF cuts.

Figure 4.9: Inclusive photon pile-up: p_0/mean for each p_T bin. The upper plots are fitted by a linear function; The lower plots are fitted by a log function.

Figure 4.10: Isolated photon yield per event vs event rate from ERT_4x4c data sample from $p_T = 6 - 30$ GeV. The upper plots only include shower profile cut; the lower plots include both shower profile and ToF cuts.

Figure 4.11: Isolated photon pile-up: p_0/mean for each p_T bin. The upper plots are fitted by a linear function; The lower plots are fitted by a log function.

Figure 4.12: BBC trigger efficiency with pile-up correction for PbSc (left) and PbGl (right).

4.10 BBC, ToF and Shower Profile Cut Efficiency

These efficiencies were calculated for π^0 in [93]. We just repeated the calculation here. Since there was a large background for single photons, we used the efficiencies of π^0 for single photons, with proper transformations.

The BBC trigger efficiency for π^0 was calculated by ERT_4x4b dataset since it did not require BBC trigger. The result was also corrected by the pile-up effect (Fig. 4.12). The procedure is the same as Sec. 4.9. This is the same as Sec. 8 of [93]. We used the same BBC trigger efficiency for photon as that for π^0 .

The ToF efficiency for π^0 was calculated in ERT_4x4c dataset (Fig. 4.13). It is consistent with pile-up correction, though there is large uncertainty due to extrapolation in the latter case. This is the same as used in [93]. It is difficult to calculate single photons' efficiency directly since there was a large background. We used the square root of π^0 ToF efficiency for single photons.

The shower profile cut efficiency for π^0 was calculated from the ERT_4x4c dataset (Fig. 4.14). Also due to the large background in single photons, we used the square root of efficiency for π^0 as that efficiency for single photons.

Figure 4.13: ToF efficiency without pile-up correction for PbSc (left) and PbGl (right).

Figure 4.14: Shower profile cut efficiency for PbSc (left) and PbGl (right). Points are from our calculation; lines are from run 13 π^0 analysis [93].

4.11 Photon Conversion

Photon conversion effect in data from 2002–2005 was estimated in the [100] and was found $(6 \pm 2)\%$ in PbSc and $(8.8 \pm 2.5)\%$ in PbGl. In run 13, VTX introduced additional material near the beam pipe. All that is implemented in PISA framework [97], which showed 14–15% of radiation length X0 for the collision vertex $|z| < 10$ cm, see fig. 24 of [93]. The discussion with experts (Y. Akiba) led to a slightly lower value for the VTX material budget of $\sim 12\%$. Hence, in this analysis, we used $(14.5 \pm 2.5)\%$. 14.5% of X0 material led to a $(14.5 \pm 2.5) \times 7/9 = (12.8 \pm 1.9)\%$ probability for a photon to convert. Note, once a photon converts in VTX material it will be vetoed by DC charge veto because the conversion electron and positron are considerably deflected in the magnetic field.

4.12 ERT_4x4c Trigger Efficiency

The ERT_4x4c trigger efficiency was calculated by using the ERT sample itself. The other arm was required to be triggered by another particle (Fig. 4.15). As in π^0 case, ERT_4x4b was normalized to ERT_4x4c data for $p_T > 14$ GeV when the trigger efficiency reach plateau (Fig. 4.16, see Sec. 4.18.8).

4.13 π^0 Missing One Photon Ratio

Due to energy threshold, finite acceptance, and EMCal warn map, sometimes we got only one photon from π^0 decay but missed the other one. This was corrected by π^0 missing one photon ratio, which was calculated by single π^0 events + fast MC as follows:

1. Generated single π^0 events with flat p_T from 0 to 40 GeV/c and flat $|\eta| < 0.5$ distribution.
2. Let π^0 decay to two photons by *TGenPhaseSpace* in ROOT [101].
3. Used fast MC to simulate detector geometry, EMCal warn map (same as data), and energy deposit of photon clusters (by some statistical distributions and response functions).

Figure 4.15: ERT_4x4c efficiency for PbSc West (black circles), PbSc East (red squares), and PbG1 (green triangles). The constant fittings are for $p_T > 10$ GeV and shown for the three detect parts from up to down.

Figure 4.16: ERT_4x4b normalization for PbSc West (left), PbSc East (middle), and PbG1 (right).

Figure 4.17: π^0 and η missing one photon ratio from fast MC for PbSc West (black circles), PbSc East (red squares), and PbGl (green triangles).

4. If the two decay photons were in acceptance and pass the warn map, and two peaks were reconstructed from EMCAL clusters, it meant we got two separated (unmerged) photons. Its number was denoted by $N_{2\gamma}$.
5. If only one photon was in acceptance and pass warn map, it meant we missed its partner photon. Its number was denoted by $N_{1\gamma}$.
6. Missing ratio was defined to be $R = N_{1\gamma}/N_{2\gamma}$ and shown in Fig. 4.17.
7. All yields were weighted by π^0 p_T distribution.
8. The same calculation was done for η mesons.

4.14 High- p_T π^0 Decay Photons Merging

The π^0 decay photons have opening angle $\theta \sim m/p_T$. At high- p_T , the opening angle will be so small that the EMCAL towers cannot separate the two clusters of π^0 decay photons. This is called photons merging. The PISA does not simulate this effect correctly. But this effect was simulated and corrected well in fast MC (Fig. 4.18).

Figure 4.18: Two photons merging rate for PbSc (black circles), PbGl (red squares). Points are from our calculation; lines are from run 13 π^0 cross section analysis [93].

In π^0 measurement, merged photons were excluded since they cannot be reconstructed. In direct photon measurement, merged photons can behave like direct photon showers. But most of them were cut by photon_prob cut. We used single π^0 events + fast MC to calculate the fraction of merged photons as follows:

1. Generated single π^0 events with flat p_T from 0 to 40 GeV/c and flat $|\eta| < 0.5$ distribution.
2. Let π^0 decay to two photons by *TGenPhaseSpace* in ROOT [101].
3. Used fast MC to simulate detector geometry, EMCal warn map (same as data), and energy deposit of photon clusters (by some statistical distributions and response functions).
4. If the two decay photons were in acceptance and pass the warn map, but only one peak was reconstructed from EMCal clusters, it meant the two photons were merged.

5. The ratio of the number of merged photons (count as one cluster) over that of two separated photons (count as two clusters) in acceptance, was the merging rate. This was calculated separately for single photons $p_T^{1\gamma}$ and photon pairs $p_T^{2\gamma}$ (see Fig. 4.19) as used in direct photon yield calculation (Sec. 4.7). In this case, two merged photons were counted as one, since they would behave like one photon if passed the shower shape cut.
6. All yields were weighted by π^0 p_T distribution.

We used single π^0 events + PISA to calculate the fraction of merged photons which passed the photon_prob cut as follows:

1. Generated single π^0 events with flat p_T from 0 to 40 GeV/c and flat $|\eta| < 0.5$ distribution.
2. Let π^0 decay to two photons in PISA [97].
3. For the truth “track” of each photon, we associated to it the EMCal cluster into which it deposits most of its energy.
4. If we got two truth photon “tracks”, and the same cluster were associated to them, then we would recognize it as a merged cluster.
5. Among all merged clusters, we calculated their prob_photon values and saw how many portions passed the prob_photon cut, as in Fig. 4.20.
6. All yields were weighted by π^0 p_T distribution.

4.15 Backgrounds Decay Photons From Other Hadrons

Other than π^0 , other hadrons (mainly η , ω , and η') also decay to photons. These photons also contribute to the backgrounds of direct photons. Rather than measured them directly, we counted the decay photons from hadrons other than π^0 by finding the photon ratio with decay photons from π^0 . This ratio was calculated by the hadron production ratio times the photon branching ratio. Since the hadron production ratio is not changed too much from $\sqrt{s} = 200$ GeV to 510 GeV based on PYTHIA simulation (right of Fig. 4.21),

Figure 4.19: π^0 two photons merging rate w.r.t. single photons $p_T^{1\gamma}$ (left) and photon pairs $p_T^{2\gamma}$ (right) for PbSc West (black circles), PbSc East (red squares), and PbGl (green triangles).

Figure 4.20: Fraction of merged photons which passed shower shape cut for PbSc (black circles), PbGl (red squares) within $|\eta| < 0.25$.

Figure 4.21: Left plot: hadron production ratios from PYTHIA, 200 GeV data and Tsallis fitting of 200 GeV data. Right plot: PYTHIA simulation of ratio of hadron production ratio between 510 GeV and 200 GeV.

Particle	Production ratio	Branching ratio	γ ratio
$\frac{\eta}{\pi^0}$	0.5 ± 0.1	$\frac{Br(\eta \rightarrow 2\gamma \pi^+ \pi^- \gamma)}{Br(\pi^0 \rightarrow 2\gamma)} = \frac{39.4 + 4.2/2}{98.8}$	0.21 ± 0.04
$\frac{\omega}{\pi^0}$	0.8 ± 0.3	$\frac{Br(\omega \rightarrow \pi^0 \gamma)}{Br(\pi^0 \rightarrow 2\gamma)} = \frac{8.4/2}{98.8}$	0.034 ± 0.013
$\frac{\eta'}{\pi^0}$	0.2 ± 0.1	$\frac{Br(\eta' \rightarrow \rho^0 \gamma \omega \gamma 2\gamma)}{Br(\pi^0 \rightarrow 2\gamma)} = \frac{28.9/2 + 2.6/2 + 2.2}{98.8}$	0.036 ± 0.018
Sum	-	-	0.28 ± 0.05

Table 4.2: Photon ratio from other hadrons.

we calculate the hadron production ratio based on 200 GeV data¹ (left of Fig. 4.21 and Tab. 4.2).

For the isolated direct photon yield, we also need the η meson self-veto V in Eq. 4.6. If the two photons from $\eta \rightarrow 2\gamma$ decay were both in acceptance, we got the ratio of the number of photons passed the isolation cut with and without including the energy of its partner photon when applying the isolation cut, this fraction was V and shown in Fig. 4.22. Here we calculated V by using only $\eta \rightarrow 2\gamma$ decay since this is the main contribution of photons

¹PYTHIA reproduced pseudoscalar meson η and η' ratio well, but not for vector meson ω . This was due to that the string model is not particularly predictive for the relative ratio between pseudoscalar and vector mesons.

Figure 4.22: η meson self-veto for PbSc West (black circles), PbSc East (red squares), PbGl (green triangles), and the combined results (purple inverted triangles). Isoboth (isopair) means passing the isolation cut with (without) including the energy of its partner photon when applying the isolation cut.

from other hadrons' decays.

4.16 Acceptance

4.16.1 Inclusive Direct Photon Acceptance

We used single photon events + fast MC to calculate the inclusive direct photon acceptance as follows:

1. Generated single photon events with flat p_T from 0 to 40 GeV/c and flat $|\eta| < 0.5$ distribution.
2. Used fast MC to simulate detector geometry, EMCal warnmap (same as data) and energy deposit of photon clusters (by some statistical distributions and response functions).

Figure 4.23: η distribution normalized by the counts of data for PbSc west (left plot), PbSc east (middle plot) and PbG1 (right plot) separately. The red points are from data and blue lines are from fast MC.

3. Compared the η and ϕ distributions between fast MC and data to validate the simulation (Fig. 4.23 and Fig. 4.24).
4. Calculated the acceptance by taking the ratio of number of reconstructed photons in acceptance with the warn map w.r.t. p_T^{reco} , and that of all generated truth photons w.r.t. p_T^{truth} (Fig. 4.25). This acceptance also included p_T -smearing due to detector resolution.
5. All yields were weighted by direct photon p_T distribution.

4.16.2 Isolated Direct Photon Acceptance

We wanted to measure isolated direct photon cross section and to compare it with next-to-leading order (NLO) calculation, which can calculate differential cross sections for mid-rapidity and different p_T bins. It can also add an isolation cut with a specific cone size $r_{cone} = \sqrt{(\delta\eta)^2 + (\delta\phi)^2}$ (Sec. 4.5). However, it did not include PHENIX detector acceptance and EMCal warn map, both for the direct photon and for the particles inside the isolation cone (when summing their energies). We used PYTHIA + fast MC to correct the detector effects as follows:

1. Used PYTHIA (with configurations in Tab. 4.3) to generate direct photon events¹.

¹We used various p_T lower cuts (CKIN3) and p_T upper cuts (CKIN4), the yield was weighted by direct photon p_T distribution.

Figure 4.24: ϕ distribution normalized by the counts of data for PbSc west (left plot), PbSc east (first two of the right plot) and PbGl (last two of the right plot) separately. The red points are from data and blue lines are from fast MC.

Figure 4.25: Inclusive photon acceptance for PbSc West (black circles), PbSc East (red squares), and PbGl (green triangles).

2. Looped for all outgoing particles, selected a particle if it was a direct photon (from its truth information in PYTHIA) and within $|\eta| < 0.25$ (from the measurement range in data).
3. We first applied isolation cut to this direct photon without detector acceptance requirement, by summing over the truth energy of all particles around this direct photon within cone size $r_{\text{cone}} = \sqrt{(\delta\eta)^2 + (\delta\phi)^2} = 0.5$. We counted how many direct photons passed this isolation cut, which was the truth yield $N_{\text{truth}}(p_T^{\text{truth}})$.
4. We then checked whether this direct photon was in PHENIX detector acceptance and passed the EMCAL warn map. If it did, we used the fast MC to get its reconstructed p_T^{reco} .
5. For a direct photon in acceptance, we applied isolation cut to it with detector acceptance requirement, by summing over the truth kinetic energy¹ of all particles around this direct photon within cone size $r_{\text{cone}} = \sqrt{(\delta\eta)^2 + (\delta\phi)^2} = 0.5$, as well as in PHENIX detector acceptance and passing the EMCAL warn map. We count how many direct photons pass this isolation cut, which is the reconstructed yield $N_{\text{reco}}(p_T^{\text{reco}})$.
6. To validate the simulation, we plotted the η (Fig. 4.26) and ϕ (Fig. 4.27) distributions between data and simulation, for reconstructed direct photons².
7. The isolated direct photon acceptance was $N_{\text{reco}}(p_T^{\text{reco}})/N_{\text{truth}}(p_T^{\text{truth}})$ (Fig. 4.28), weighted by direct photon p_T distribution.

4.17 Direct Photon Cross Section Results

4.17.1 Inclusive Direct Photon Cross Section Results

The inclusive direct photon cross section was calculated according to Eq. 4.1 and shown in Tab. 4.4 and Fig. 4.30. As a consistency check, it was first

¹Since we did not implement hadron response well in fast MC, we used truth kinetic energy for a particle if we did not know whether it was photon or not.

²The simulation here was from PYTHIA with MinBias configurations. However, to get more statistics, we used direct photon events to calculate acceptance

```

roots    510
proj     p
targ     p
frame    cms

msel     10      // direct photons

```

Table 4.3: PYTHIA configurations for isolated direct photon acceptance.

Figure 4.26: η distribution normalized by the counts of data for PbSc west (left-plot), PbSc east (middle-plot) and PbGl (right-plot) separately. The red points are data and blue lines are fast MC.

Figure 4.27: ϕ distribution normalized by the counts of data for PbSc west (left plot), PbSc east (first two of the right plot) and PbGl (last two of the right plot) separately. The red points are data and blue lines are fast MC.

Figure 4.28: Isolated direct photon acceptance for PbSc West (black circles), PbSc East (red squares), and PbGl (green triangles).

separated for three detector parts: PbSc West, PbSc East and PbGl, and then combined (Fig. 4.29a). The normalized difference $\frac{\sigma_{\text{part}} - \sigma_{\text{combined}}}{\sigma_{\text{combined}}}$ is shown in Fig. 4.29b. The NLO pQCD calculations are shown in Fig. 4.30. The cross section ratio between the inclusive direct photon and the π^0 is shown in Fig. 4.31.

We also compared our measurements with POWHEG + PYTHIA8 predictions. POWHEG provides a way to combine NLO matrix elements with parton showers [104–106]. The NLO direct photon calculations under POWHEG were given by Ježo et al. [107, 108], where POWHEG gives NLO parton level calculations, and PYTHIA gives parton showers and multiparton interactions (MPI), with the overlapping phase space between POWHEG and PYTHIA vetoed in PYTHIA. We used the existing code to study the inclusive direct photon cross section.

NLO pQCD underestimates the inclusive direct photon cross section due to its partonic nature. We used POWHEG + PYTHIA8 to calculate the inclusive direct photon cross section with different veto algorithms, as well as w/o MPI (Fig. 4.32). The default veto algorithm uses a single scale for both QED and QCD radiations, while the QED-QCD veto algorithm uses two

p_T [GeV]	Cross section	Stat. error	Syst. error
6.2309	2321.8456	35.9557 (01.5486%)	623.4248 (26.8504%)
6.7321	1301.2920	26.1560 (02.0100%)	356.8720 (27.4244%)
7.2330	809.6827	19.0895 (02.3576%)	210.9074 (26.0482%)
7.7341	564.4147	14.0467 (02.4887%)	129.4117 (22.9285%)
8.2351	364.8362	10.8536 (02.9749%)	83.8554 (22.9844%)
8.7358	250.8143	8.2947 (03.3071%)	54.7668 (21.8356%)
9.2367	166.5620	6.6034 (03.9645%)	37.0429 (22.2397%)
9.7372	106.0030	5.2900 (04.9904%)	24.7297 (23.3292%)
10.8152	61.0831	1.8324 (02.9998%)	14.7046 (24.0731%)
12.8436	17.7600	0.8848 (04.9818%)	4.3337 (24.4012%)
14.8617	7.9693	0.2658 (03.3350%)	1.5199 (19.0723%)
16.8823	2.7048	0.1368 (05.0570%)	0.6324 (23.3822%)
18.9000	1.3111	0.0836 (06.3797%)	0.2814 (21.4656%)
20.9063	0.8033	0.1206 (15.0124%)	0.1897 (23.6139%)
22.9159	0.4969	0.0765 (15.4005%)	0.0956 (19.2335%)
24.9488	0.2487	0.0535 (21.5242%)	0.0529 (21.2634%)
26.9154	0.1736	0.0408 (23.5261%)	0.0329 (18.9424%)
28.9333	0.0864	0.0319 (36.8622%)	0.0207 (24.0028%)

Table 4.4: Inclusive direct photon cross section (pb/GeV²). The overall normalization error of 10% is not included. The bin shift correction was applied by shifting the points along the p_T axis.

Figure 4.29: Inclusive direct photon cross sections separated for PbSc West (black circles), PbSc East (red squares), and PbGl (green triangles). As a consistency check, only uncorrelated statistical uncertainties among the three parts are shown here.

separate scales for them. We see that POWHEG with default veto and MPI gives best predictions at high p_T (Fig. 4.32a), while with QED-QCD veto and MPI agrees best at low p_T , but it overestimates at high p_T and suffers large fluctuations (Fig. 4.32b). We also see the importance to include MPI, especially at low p_T (Fig. 4.32c). POWHEG without any parton shower and MPI in PYTHIA is just like NLO pQCD without fragmentation contributions (Fig. 4.32d).

4.17.2 Isolated Direct Photon Cross Section Results

The isolated direct photon cross section was calculated according to Eq. 4.1 and shown in Tab. 4.5 and Fig. 4.34. As a consistency check, it was first separated for three detector parts: PbSc West, PbSc East and PbGl, and then combined (Fig. 4.33a). The normalized difference $\frac{\sigma_{\text{part}} - \sigma_{\text{combined}}}{\sigma_{\text{combined}}}$ is shown in Fig. 4.33b. The NLO pQCD calculations are shown in right of Fig. 4.34. The cross section ratio between isolated and inclusive direct photons is shown in Fig. 4.35. The cross section ratio between the isolated direct photon and the

Figure 4.30: Inclusive direct photon cross section as a function of p_T compared with NLO pQCD calculations [102, 103] for different renormalization and factorization scales $\mu = p_T/2$ (dashed line), p_T (solid line), $2p_T$ (dotted line). The bars represent statistical uncertainties and square brackets are for systematic uncertainties. The bottom plot shows the comparison of data and calculations.

Figure 4.31: The cross section ratio between the inclusive direct photon and the π^0 , $\gamma_{\text{dir}}/\pi^0$. The uncertainty is only from statistical uncertainty of direct photon cross section.

π^0 is shown in Fig. 4.36a. The comparison with run 6 direct photon results is shown in Fig. 4.36b.

We also compared our measurements with POWHEG + PYTHIA8 predictions. We used the existing code to study the isolated direct photon cross section, as well as the cross section ratio between isolated and inclusive direct photons.

All calculations from POWHEG + PYTHIA8 with different vetoes and w/o MPI agree with the measurement in isolated direct photon cross section (Fig. 4.37), though with the default veto and MPI agrees best (Fig. 4.37a).

We also studied the isolated over inclusive direct photon ratio (Fig. 4.38). We see that only PYTHIA with QED-QCD veto and MPI agree with data for $p_T < 10$ GeV, but it suffers large fluctuations at high- p_T . All others agree with data at high- p_T , and overall PYTHIA with default veto and MPI agree best with data. PYTHIA with default veto and without MPI is just like NLO pQCD. PYTHIA with pure hard processes has flat isolated over inclusive direct photon ratio.

(a) With MPI (default veto).

(b) With MPI (QED-QCD veto).

(c) Without MPI (default veto).

(d) Pure hard processes.

Figure 4.32: POWHEG + PYTHIA8 with different vetoes and w/o MPI for the inclusive direct photon cross section.

p_T [GeV]	Cross section	Stat. error	Syst. error
6.2309	1087.6543	11.3064 (01.0395%)	114.1811 (10.4979%)
6.7321	640.3197	8.0753 (01.2611%)	64.5017 (10.0734%)
7.2330	404.6792	5.9130 (01.4612%)	38.7461 (09.5745%)
7.7341	279.4838	4.3827 (01.5681%)	24.9335 (08.9213%)
8.2351	185.4689	3.3689 (01.8164%)	17.6427 (09.5125%)
8.7358	133.1426	2.6339 (01.9782%)	12.2429 (09.1953%)
9.2367	97.6636	2.1683 (02.2202%)	8.9891 (09.2041%)
9.7372	64.9196	1.7586 (02.7088%)	6.1873 (09.5307%)
10.8152	35.8861	0.5738 (01.5990%)	3.5592 (09.9182%)
12.8436	13.2989	0.3027 (02.2763%)	1.2613 (09.4839%)
14.8617	5.8561	0.0982 (01.6764%)	0.6071 (10.3668%)
16.8823	2.8367	0.0612 (02.1572%)	0.3050 (10.7516%)
18.9000	1.3742	0.0398 (02.8959%)	0.1537 (11.1865%)
20.9063	0.7910	0.0279 (03.5289%)	0.0881 (11.1368%)
22.9159	0.4473	0.0198 (04.4360%)	0.0545 (12.1884%)
24.9488	0.2639	0.0151 (05.7069%)	0.0364 (13.7906%)
26.9154	0.1517	0.0114 (07.5027%)	0.0183 (12.0899%)
28.9333	0.0967	0.0096 (09.9315%)	0.0133 (13.7186%)

Table 4.5: Isolated direct photon cross section (pb/GeV²). The overall normalization error of 10% is not included. The bin shift correction was applied by shifting the points along the p_T axis.

(a) Cross sections. The red line is a fitting used for p_T smearing. (b) Cross section differences $\frac{\sigma_{\text{part}} - \sigma_{\text{combined}}}{\sigma_{\text{combined}}}$.

Figure 4.33: Isolated direct photon cross sections separated for PbSc West (black circles), PbSc East (red squares), and PbGl (green triangles). As a consistency check, only uncorrelated statistical uncertainties among the three parts are shown here.

4.18 Systematic Uncertainties for Direct Photon Cross Section

Systematic errors were estimated in a very much similar way as in run 13 π^0 cross section [93]. The dominant systematic uncertainties are connected with the EMCAL energy scale (energy global scale and energy nonlinearity). Below I briefly review different uncertainty sources.

4.18.1 Global Energy Scale, Geometrical Misalignment and Energy Nonlinearity

Energy global scale was established by tuning π^0 mass peak position at p_T about 4 GeV to what is expected from MC after simulation of energy smearing effect due to EMCAL limited resolutions, and taking into account the possible effect of reconstructed π^0 mass peak shift by (-1 ± 1) MeV due to photon conversion and other π^0 Dalitz decay $\pi^0 \rightarrow \gamma e^+ e^-$, as obtained from PISA

Figure 4.34: Isolated direct photon cross section: bars are statistical uncertainties and square brackets are systematic uncertainties. NLO pQCD calculations [102, 103] are shown as lines with different renormalization and factorization scales. The lower plot shows comparison of data and the calculations.

Figure 4.35: The cross section ratio between isolated and inclusive direct photons: bars are statistical uncertainties and square brackets are systematic uncertainties. POWHEG + PYTHIA8 w/o MPI and NLO pQCD calculations with different renormalization and factorization scales are also shown.

(a) Isolated $\gamma_{\text{dir}}/\pi^0$ from this analysis. The uncertainty is only from statistical uncertainty of direct photon cross section. (b) $\gamma_{\text{dir}}/\pi^0$ from run 6 direct photon analysis (Fig. 12 of [99]).

Figure 4.36: The cross section ratio between the isolated direct photon and the π^0 , $\gamma_{\text{dir}}/\pi^0$, for this measurement (left) and run 6 measurement (right).

full MC simulation [100]. This value was ~ 137 MeV (c.f. App. A). The p_T around 4 GeV was selected to get enough π^0 statistics (the lower p_T the better) and to get rid of tower energy threshold effects at lower p_T (the higher p_T the better).

π^0 mass peak reconstruction involves not only energy measurements in the EMCal but also EMCal geometry. There is an indication that EMCal geometry is surprisingly not well defined (e.g. distance between EMCal and beam line). This uncertainty directly propagated to the reconstructed π^0 mass peak. And this possible geometrical misalignment is also consistent with the observed excess of the measured π^0 and direct photon yields in PbGl compared to PbSc in all previous years. However, in this analysis, such a discrepancy is much smaller. Since this misalignment has not yet been confirmed from EMCal geometry survey measurements, this effect is not corrected, but included in systematic uncertainties. So the final systematic uncertainty for the EMCal global energy scale is defined to be 1.2% (see e.g. [109, 110]): 1% from possible EMCal geometrical misalignment and 0.7% due to photon conversion and other photon sources, added in quadrature.

(a) With MPI (default veto).

(b) With MPI (QED-QCD veto).

(c) Without MPI (default veto).

(d) Pure hard processes.

Figure 4.37: POWHEG + PYTHIA8 with different vetoes and w/o MPI for the isolated direct photon cross section.

Figure 4.38: POWHEG + PYTHIA8 with different vetoes and w/o MPI for cross section ratio between isolated and inclusive direct photons.

Energy nonlinearity mainly affects the highest p_T bins. This uncertainty was borrowed from Run 3 analysis [100].

These systematic uncertainties were calculated by single photon/ π^0 events + fast MC simulations as follow:

1. Generated single photon/ π^0 events with flat p_T from 0 to 40 GeV/c and flat $|\eta| < 0.5$ distribution.
2. Used fast MC to simulate detector geometry, EMCal warn map (same as data), and energy deposit of photon clusters (by some statistical distributions and response functions).
3. Calculated the reconstructed photon yield $N_{\text{default}}^\gamma$ and π^0 yield $N_{\text{default}}^{\pi^0}$ with default fast MC configurations as in acceptance calculation (Sec. 4.16).
4. Tuned different responses in fast MC for studying different systematic errors:

- Global energy scale: scaled the output energy of any photon clusters by factor 0.993.
- Geometrical misalignment: shifted the coordinates of impacted towers by 1%.
- Energy nonlinearity: increased the power for light attenuation by 2./300. (below *et1* is the cluster energy in GeV).

```

|| et1 *= pow(et1, -2./800.+2./300.); // for PbSc
|| et1 *= pow(et1/2, +2./120.+2./300.); // for PbGl

```

5. Calculated the reconstructed photon yield N_{tune}^γ and π^0 yield $N_{\text{tune}}^{\pi^0}$ with each of above tuned fast MC configurations.
6. The relative systematic uncertainty for direct photon yield is $\Delta r^\gamma = |N_{\text{tune}}^\gamma/N_{\text{default}}^\gamma - 1|$ (left plot of Fig. 4.39) and that for π^0 yield is $\Delta r^{\pi^0} = |N_{\text{tune}}^{\pi^0}/N_{\text{default}}^{\pi^0} - 1|$ (right plot of Fig. 4.39).
7. In data, the direct photon yield was calculated by subtracting the π^0 yield from the total photon yield, as in Eq. 4.3 for the inclusive direct photon and Eq. 4.6 for the isolated direct photon. Varying the direct photon and π^0 yields in data independently (then sum in quadrature) and using Δr^γ and Δr^{π^0} from the previous step, we got the systematic

(a) Single photon events.

(b) Single π^0 events.

Figure 4.39: Relative systematic uncertainties for global energy scale (red squares), energy nonlinearity (green triangle upss), geometrical misalignment (blue triangle downs) and quadrature sum of all three (black lines) from fast MC.

uncertainties that propagate to direct photon cross section (red solid line in Fig. 4.43).

4.18.2 EMCal Resolution

This affects the measured direct photon cross section via the smearing effect. The collected π^0 statistics is enough to tune the EMCal energy resolution parameters to the real ones using measured π^0 peak width vs p_T : low p_T π^0 's are sensitive to fluctuation term in the energy resolution parametrization; higher p_T π^0 's are sensitive to the constant term. So the final effect of uncertainty of EMCal resolutions (energy and position) to π^0 cross section measurements was found to be $< 2\%$ in all p_T bins [93]. We propagated this uncertainty to direct photon cross section by varying the π^0 yield 2%.

4.18.3 π^0 Yield Extraction

π^0 yield extraction uncertainty mainly comes from the background subtraction (Sec. 4.8), which is defined by fitting the invariant mass distribution

outside the π^0 peak region. This uncertainty was calculated from the difference between fitting with gaus+pol3 vs Gaussian Process for Regression (GPR, see [111]). We plot these fittings in Fig. 4.40 (Fig. 4.40) for the PbSc (PbGl), from which the difference of π^0 “signal” fraction $r_{\text{sig}} = \frac{N_{\pi^0}}{N_{\pi^0} + N_{\text{bg}}}$ between GPR and gaus+pol3 fitting $\Delta r_{\text{sig}} = r_{\text{sig}}^{\text{GPR}} - r_{\text{sig}}^{\text{gaus+pol3}}$ vs p_T is shown in Fig. 4.42. When calculating the direct photon yield, we varied the π^0 yield $\Delta N_{\pi^0} = N_{\pi^0} \Delta r_{\text{sig}}$ by the difference between these two fittings. Green solid line in Fig. 4.43 shows how they propagated to direct photon cross section. The isolation cut can reduce the π^0 background for the direct photons, so the systematic errors with isolation cut is much smaller than that without isolation cut.

4.18.4 Other Hadron Production Ratio

We used $\sqrt{s} = 200$ GeV data for η , ω and η' production ratio. The results from 200 GeV were fitted with a Tsallis distribution. The uncertainties for the Tsallis distribution were assigned as systematic uncertainties as in Tab. 4.2. The Blue dashed line in Fig. 4.43 shows how they propagated to direct photon cross section.

4.18.5 Shower Merging

Comparison of the reconstructed direct photon cross section in PbSc and PbGl at higher $p_T > 10$ GeV is a key test to check the correctness of the merging corrections. As shown in Fig. 4.29b and Fig. 4.33b, the obtained direct photon cross section from PbSc and PbGl are in good agreement, indicating no issues in merging corrections applied to the data. So we only assigned the statistical uncertainty from simulation (Fig. 4.19) as systematic uncertainty of merging effect.

4.18.6 Geometrical Acceptance

This comes from the simulations for direct photon acceptance and π^0 's and η 's decay photons missing ratio. Due to the limited statistics for simulation, this is $<0.5\%$ ($<1\%$) for the inclusive (isolated) direct photon.

Figure 4.40: Yield of photon pairs in PbSc vs their invariant mass m_{inv} for each p_T . The gaus+pol3 fittings are shown as red lines, of which the pol3 part is the background, shown as green lines. The black circles are predictions from GPR fittings of the sideband region.

Figure 4.41: Yield of photon pairs in PhI vs their invariant mass m_{inv} for each p_T . The gaus+pol3 fittings are shown as red lines, of which the pol3 part is the background, shown as green lines. The black circles are predictions from GPR fittings of the sideband region.

Figure 4.42: Difference of π^0 “signal” fraction $r_{\text{sig}} = \frac{N_{\pi^0}}{N_{\pi^0} + N_{\text{bg}}}$ between GPR and gaus+pol3 fitting $\Delta r_{\text{sig}} = r_{\text{sig}}^{\text{GPR}} - r_{\text{sig}}^{\text{gaus+pol3}}$ vs p_T . For $p_T > 10$ GeV, we used $\Delta r_{\text{sig}} = 0.05$ since there is large statistical fluctuation.

4.18.7 Photon Conversion

Photon conversion effect, as from [112], is $(6 \pm 2)\%$ in PbSc and $(8.8 \pm 2.5)\%$ in PbGl. In run13 VTX introduced additional conversion material in the West Arm of $\sim 14.5\%$ of radiation length X_0 . The uncertainty for the photon loss due to VTX material is 1.9% as in Sec. 4.11. It is 1–8% (0.5–2.5%) after propagating to inclusive (isolated) direct photon cross section.

4.18.8 ERT Trigger Efficiency and Normalization

ERT_4x4c data sample is included in the final direct photon cross section results from $p_T > 6$ GeV, where ERT_4x4c trigger efficiency is well defined. This plateau level (at > 8 GeV in PbSc and > 9.5 GeV in PbGl) is defined and confirmed from MC (accounting for the masked trigger tiles/SMs) with an accuracy better than 2%. However, additional uncertainty may appear for the lower p_T region, where the efficiency has not yet reached a plateau level, and which is hard to precisely simulate. Here we can estimate the uncertainty

from the comparison between two methods to calculate (from ERT sample itself and MB). This comparison doesn't reveal any inconsistencies, hence we didn't assign any additional systematic uncertainty to the ERT_4x4c trigger efficiency for the p_T region used in the final cross section (> 6 GeV).

ERT_4x4c data normalization relative to MB data was obtained from the calculation of the number of underlying MB events in the ERT_4x4c sample, which is the number of ERT_4x4c events times ERT_4x4c trigger rejection power, defined as the number of MB events divided by the number of MB&ERT_4x4c events, in the MB data sample. Another way is to directly extract the number of the underlying MB events from the database (corrected by the ERT_4x4c trigger scale down), although without the possibility to explicitly apply the offline vertex cut, as we do in the cross section data analysis. However, both methods agreed within 1.5%, indicating no issues in the extraction of the ERT_4x4c normalization factor. We assigned the difference between these two methods as the systematic uncertainty of ERT_4x4c normalization.

At higher p_T (> 14 GeV) we used higher threshold ERT_4x4b triggered data (the region where ERT_4x4b trigger efficiency plateaus). It provides a factor of ~ 3 more statistics than ERT_4x4c because it is not scaled down in run 13, while ERT_4x4c is on the average scaled down by a factor of ~ 3 . The ERT_4x4b direct photon yield is normalized to ERT_4x4c data, hence we didn't explicitly measure its rejection factor and efficiency. The normalization factors (0.321 in PbSc and 0.243 in PbGl, see Fig. 4.16) are defined with precisions better than 1% and reflected not only the average scale down of ERT_4x4c sample but also the difference in the trigger coverage: while the number of masked SM between ERT_4x4c and ERT_4x4b triggers is the same for PbSc, in PbGl the number of masked SMs decreases from 21 in 4x4c to 7 in ERT_4x4b (hence, efficiency increases in ERT_4x4b). We use the fitting uncertainty in Fig. 4.16 as the systematic uncertainty of ERT_4x4b normalization.

4.18.9 MB Trigger Bias

The pile-up corrected BBC efficiency is shown in Fig. 4.12 and fitted with a constant. The fitting value is 0.91 with a uncertainty less than 0.01. As a result, we used 0.91 value with 0.01 uncertainty.

Source	Inclusive rel. syst. error	Isolated rel. syst. error
Global energy scale and geometrical misalignment and energy nonlinearity	14–19%	7–13%
EMCal resolution	2–8%	0.3–3%
π^0 yield extraction	2–12%	0.5–2.5%
η , ω and η' prod. ratio	5–14%	0.4–6%
Geometrical acceptance	<0.5%	<1%
Photon conversion	1–8%	0.5–2.5%
ERT efficiency and normalization	2–4.5%	2–4.5%
MB trigger bias	1%	1%
Pile-up effect	1%	2%

Table 4.6: Summary of relative systematic uncertainties in inclusive and isolated direct photon cross sections.

4.18.10 Pile-up Effect

The systematic uncertainty on pile-up is from the fitting uncertainty and difference between linear fit and log fit in Fig. 4.9 for inclusive and Fig. 4.11 for isolated direct photon yield. 1% (2%) uncertainty was assigned for inclusive (isolated) direct photon cross section.

4.18.11 Summary of Systematic Uncertainties

The systematic uncertainties are summarized in Tab. 4.6. The main systematic errors come from the global energy scale and energy nonlinearity.

(a) Inclusive cross section.

(b) Isolated cross section.

Figure 4.43: Relative systematic uncertainties in inclusive (left) and isolated (right) direct photon cross sections. Black points show total systematic uncertainties in each data p_T point (10% global scale uncertainty due to MB trigger cross section uncertainty is not included). Red solid line: the quadratic sum of global energy scale, geometrical misalignment and energy nonlinearity. Green solid line: π^0 yield extraction. Blue dashed line: photons from hadrons other than π^0 . Yellow dashed line: PID efficiency (shower profile and ToF). Magenta dashed line: the quadratic sum of EMCAL resolutions, geometrical acceptance (not correlated with geometrical misalignment), missing ratio, η meson self-veto (in isolated cross section), photons merging rate, photon conversion, MB trigger bias, ERT trigger efficiency and normalization, and event overlap correction uncertainty.

Chapter 5

Direct Photon A_{LL} Analysis

The longitudinal double-spin asymmetry is measured as

$$A_{LL} = \frac{\Delta\sigma}{\sigma} = \frac{\sigma_{++} + \sigma_{--} - \sigma_{+-} - \sigma_{-+}}{\sigma_{++} + \sigma_{--} + \sigma_{+-} + \sigma_{-+}}, \quad (5.1)$$

where σ_{++} (σ_{+-}) is the cross section for the same (opposite) helicity proton collisions. As a shorthand, we write $++$ ($+-$) for both $++$ and $--$ ($+-$ and $-+$). Eq. 5.1 can be rewritten in terms of particle yield (N) and luminosity (\mathcal{L}) assuming that all efficiencies are helicity independent and that the beam polarizations are the same for $++$ and $+-$. This gives

$$A_{LL} = \frac{1}{P_B P_Y} \frac{N_{++} - RN_{+-}}{N_{++} + RN_{+-}}, \quad (5.2)$$

where $P_{B(Y)}$ is the polarization of the RHIC blue (yellow) beam and R is the relative luminosity which is defined as

$$R = \frac{\mathcal{L}_{++}}{\mathcal{L}_{+-}}. \quad (5.3)$$

Main luminosity detector of this analysis is BBC. With a assumption that the proton-proton cross section for BBC trigger is the same for both $++$ and $+-$ crossing, Eq. 5.3 can rewritten as

$$R = \frac{\mathcal{L}_{++}^{\text{BBC}}}{\mathcal{L}_{+-}^{\text{BBC}}}. \quad (5.4)$$

Systematic uncertainty from the assumption is discussed in [113].

5.1 Photon Selection for A_{LL}

There are ghost clusters from previous crossings, which give false asymmetry (see Sec. 3.1 of [114] and Sec. 3.2.1 of [94]). So for the clusters in the isolation cone, we also used cuts $|\text{ToF}| < 10$ ns and $E_{\text{min}} > 0.3$ GeV, as suggested in [115]. The cuts for A_{LL} measurement are the same as isolated direct photon cross section and listed in Tab. 4.1.

5.2 Backgrounds of Isolated Direct Photon A_{LL}

The isolated direct photon A_{LL}^{dir} was measured by the isolated total photon A_{LL}^{total} , subtracting the following backgrounds:

- $A_{LL}^{\pi^0}$: A_{LL} of unmerged isolated photons from π^0 's decay (To get more statistics, we used A_{LL} of inclusive decay photons). Since it is for unmerged photons, we used single photons $p_T^{1\gamma}$.
- $A_{LL}^{\pi^0}(p_T^{2\gamma})$: A_{LL} of merged isolated photons from π^0 's decay (To get more statistics, we used A_{LL} of inclusive decay photons). Since it is for merged photons (but it is measured by reconstructing unmerged photon pairs), we used photon pairs $p_T^{2\gamma}$.
- A_{LL}^h : A_{LL} of isolated photons from η 's, ω 's and η' 's decay. Most these photons are from η mesons. A_{LL}^η was measured at 200 GeV at run 5, 6 and 9 [116] and is consistent with zero. We used the combined A_{LL}^η from 200 GeV assuming x_T scaling (TABLE VII of [116]). Since decay photons from these hadrons are not merged for $p_T < 20$ GeV, we used single photons $p_T^{1\gamma}$.

The isolated direct photon A_{LL}^{dir} can be calculated as

$$A_{LL}^{\text{dir}} = \frac{A_{LL}^{\text{total}} - r_{\pi^0} A_{LL}^{\pi^0} - r_{\pi^0}(p_T^{2\gamma}) A_{LL}^{\pi^0}(p_T^{2\gamma}) - r_h A_{LL}^h}{1 - r_{\pi^0} - r_{\pi^0}(p_T^{2\gamma}) - r_h}. \quad (5.5)$$

According to the composition of isolated direct photon yield (Eq. 4.6), the

background fractions r 's of the corresponding backgrounds A_{LL} 's are

$$r_{\pi^0} = \left(1 + \frac{M(1 - \epsilon_{\text{conv}})}{\epsilon} \right) \frac{n_{\pi^0}}{n_{\text{total}}} + \frac{R}{\epsilon} \frac{N_{\pi^0}}{n_{\text{total}}}, \quad (5.6)$$

$$r_{\pi^0}(p_T^{2\gamma}) = \frac{M(p_T^{2\gamma})P(p_T^{2\gamma})}{2\epsilon_{\text{prob}}^2} \frac{N_{\pi^0}(p_T^{2\gamma})}{n_{\text{total}}}, \quad (5.7)$$

$$r_h = A'(V + \frac{R_\eta}{\epsilon}) \frac{N_{\pi^0}}{n_{\text{total}}}. \quad (5.8)$$

We can understand these background fractions as follow:

- The denominator is the number of reconstructed isolated total photons n_{total} .
- r_{π^0} : It is based on the first three subtracted terms in Eq. 4.6. The first term is the number of reconstructed isolated photons from π^0 's decay, n_{π^0} . The second term is the number of reconstructed isolated photons from π^0 's decay with their partners converted, $M\epsilon_{\text{conv}}(1 - \epsilon_{\text{conv}})\frac{n_{\pi^0}}{\epsilon^2} \cdot \epsilon_{\text{prob}}\epsilon_{\text{ToF}}$, since their partners were converted and no need to be reconstructed. The third term is the number of reconstructed photons from π^0 's decay with their partners missed, $\frac{R}{\epsilon^2}N_{\pi^0} \cdot \epsilon$ since their partners are missed and no need to be reconstructed.
- $r_{\pi^0}(p_T^{2\gamma})$: It is based on the merged photons in Eq. 4.6, $\frac{M(p_T^{2\gamma})P(p_T^{2\gamma})}{2} \frac{N_{\pi^0}(p_T^{2\gamma})}{\epsilon^2} (\epsilon_{\text{conv}}\epsilon_{\text{ToF}})^2$, since they were not converted and passed the ToF cut, but the prob_photon cut efficiency ϵ_{prob} was considered in $P(p_T^{2\gamma})$.
- r_h : It is based on the photons from other hadrons' decay in Eq. 4.6, $A'(\frac{V}{\epsilon^2} \cdot \epsilon^2 + \frac{R_\eta}{\epsilon^2} \cdot \epsilon)N_{\pi^0}$, since the first term need to reconstruct two photons, while the second term only need to reconstruct one photon.

The statistical uncertainties of the background fractions Δr 's are calculated by error propagation as in Eq. 4.5. Those of the A_{LL} 's are discussed in the following subsections.

5.3 π^0 A_{LL} as the Background

The π^0 A_{LL} was calculated in the same way as in run 13 π^0 A_{LL} analysis [94]. Here we recalculated it by using both the single photons $p_T^{1\gamma}$ for unmerged

decay photons, $A_{LL}^{\pi^0}$, and the photon pairs $p_T^{2\gamma}$ for merged decay photons, $A_{LL}^{\pi^0}(p_T^{2\gamma})$. The A_{LL}^{run} of each run was calculated by Eq. 5.1 with statistical constraints

$$N_{++} + N_{+-} \geq 10 \quad (5.9)$$

in the ‘‘peak’’ region and

$$N_{++} \geq 1 \&\& N_{+-} \geq 1 \quad (5.10)$$

in the ‘‘sideband’’ region. The statistical uncertainty of A_{LL}^{run} of each run is

$$\begin{aligned} (\Delta A_{LL}^{\text{run}})^2 = & \left(\frac{1}{P_B P_Y} \frac{2RN_{++}N_{+-}}{(N_{++} + RN_{+-})^2} \right)^2 \left(\left(\frac{\Delta N_{++}}{N_{++}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta N_{+-}}{N_{+-}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta R}{R} \right)^2 \right) \\ & + \left(\left(\frac{\Delta P_B}{P_B} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta P_Y}{P_Y} \right)^2 \right) (A_{LL}^{\text{run}})^2. \end{aligned} \quad (5.11)$$

As in [94], we separated runs by even and odd crossings and four spin patterns (eight groups). We fit A_{LL}^{run} vs run for each group with a constant to get A_{LL}^{group} for each crossing and spin pattern. Then we do F-test to confirm A_{LL}^{group} 's of the eight groups are consistent. F, defined as $\frac{\text{between-group variability}}{\text{within-group variability}}$, is the deviation between A_{LL}^{group} 's of the 8 groups, in the unit of the statistical variance $(\Delta A_{LL})^2$ of all runs. Its corresponding statistical significance is p. $p < 0.05$ means a significant discrepancy between A_{LL}^{group} 's of the 8 groups. The F-test results for $A_{LL}^{\pi^0}$ depending on the signal photon $p_T^{1\gamma}$ and the photon pair $p_T^{2\gamma}$ are shown in Tab. 5.1 and Tab. 5.2, respectively. Finally, we combined them to get the final $A_{LL}^{\pi^0}$ (Fig. 5.1 and Fig. 5.2).

5.4 Isolated Direct Photon A_{LL} after Background Subtraction

As for π^0 $A_{LL}^{\pi^0}$, we followed the same procedures to calculate isolated total photon A_{LL}^{total} . The A_{LL}^{run} of each run was calculated by Eq. 5.1 with statistical constraint (Eq. 5.9). We separated runs by even and odd crossings and four spin patterns (eight groups). We fit A_{LL}^{run} vs run for each group with a constant to get A_{LL}^{group} for each crossing and spin pattern. Fig. 5.3 shows the fitting for one of the four spin patterns with even crossing number. Then we did F-test to confirm A_{LL}^{group} 's of the eight groups are consistent (Tab. 5.3). By

p_T [GeV]	F	p	p_T [GeV]	F	p
2-2.5	2.338	0.02248	2-2.5	1.301	0.246
2.5-3	1.887	0.06797	2.5-3	2.377	0.02035
3-3.5	0.8076	0.5809	3-3.5	1.078	0.3747
3.5-4	1.361	0.2179	3.5-4	0.8329	0.5599
4-4.5	1.634	0.1214	4-4.5	1.174	0.3142
4.5-5	0.3967	0.9047	4.5-5	1.379	0.2101
5-6	0.9777	0.4457	5-6	0.5081	0.829
6-7	1.113	0.3522	6-7	0.5101	0.8275
7-8	0.2164	0.9817	7-8	1.159	0.3234
8-9	1.034	0.405	8-9	0.2023	0.985
9-10	1.002	0.4277	9-10	1.14	0.3351
10-12	1.81	0.08138	10-12	1.771	0.08905
12-15	0.6034	0.7535	12-15	1.81	0.08156
15-20	1.561	0.1441	15-20	1.677	0.1118

(a) Peak region

(b) Sideband region

Table 5.1: F-test of $\pi^0 A_{LL}^{\pi^0}(p_T^{1\gamma})$.

p_T [GeV]	F	p	p_T [GeV]	F	p
2-2.5	0.9261	0.485	2-2.5	2.091	0.04165
2.5-3	2.118	0.03895	2.5-3	2.329	0.02297
3-3.5	2.317	0.02367	3-3.5	0.8123	0.577
3.5-4	1.7	0.1047	3.5-4	0.6907	0.68
4-4.5	1.527	0.1536	4-4.5	1.176	0.3135
4.5-5	2.168	0.03443	4.5-5	0.3058	0.9515
5-6	1.013	0.4196	5-6	0.7298	0.6467
6-7	2.113	0.0394	6-7	0.6903	0.6804
7-8	1.292	0.2506	7-8	0.7964	0.5903
8-9	1.61	0.1283	8-9	0.8741	0.5262
9-10	0.9137	0.4947	9-10	1.208	0.2949
10-12	1.296	0.2486	10-12	0.7092	0.6643
12-15	0.4701	0.8567	12-15	0.9563	0.4618
15-20	1.453	0.1804	15-20	2.47	0.0161

(a) Peak region

(b) Sideband region

Table 5.2: F-test of $A_{LL}^{\pi^0}(p_T^{2\gamma})$.

Figure 5.1: $A_{LL}^{\pi^0}(p_T^{1\gamma})$ vs single photons $p_T^{1\gamma}$ for signal+background (upper-left), background (upper-right) and signal (lower-left) separated for different spin patterns and even/odd crossings, and for signal (lower-right) combined for spin patterns and crossings.

Figure 5.2: $A_{LL}^{\pi^0}(p_T^{2\gamma})$ vs photon pairs $p_T^{2\gamma}$ for signal+background (upper-left), background (upper-right) and signal (lower-left) separated for different spin patterns and even/odd crossings, and for signal (lower-right) combined for spin patterns and crossings.

p_T [GeV]	F	p
2-2.5	1.125	0.3445
2.5-3	3.452	0.001132
3-3.5	4.174	0.0001452
3.5-4	2.546	0.01316
4-4.5	1.545	0.1477
4.5-5	1.501	0.1624
5-6	0.6462	0.7178
6-7	1.047	0.3962
7-8	0.9306	0.4815
8-9	0.6235	0.7369
9-10	1.434	0.1875
10-12	0.8384	0.5553
12-15	0.7312	0.6455
15-20	0.812	0.5773

Table 5.3: F-test of isolated total photon A_{LL}^{total} .

using Eq. 5.5, we got the isolated direct photon A_{LL}^{dir} from the isolated total photon A_{LL}^{total} and the π^0 $A_{LL}^{\pi^0}$. Finally, we combined different spin patterns and crossings to get the final A_{LL}^{dir} (Fig. 5.4).

5.5 $A_{L(L)}^{\text{dir}}$ Results with Systematic Uncertainties

The $A_{L(L)}^{\text{dir}}$ with systematic uncertainties (see Sec. 5.8) are shown in Tab. 5.4, Fig. 5.5 and Fig. 5.6.

5.6 Bunch Shuffling

Bunch Shuffling is a boot-strapping technique used to extract the statistical uncertainty on A_{LL} in a model-independent way, i.e. no assumptions about underlying statistical distributions need to be assumed. The results of bunch shuffling can be checked to see if they agree with the result of our equations for calculating the uncertainty of A_{LL} . The result of such a comparison

Figure 5.3: Isolated total photon A_{LL}^{total} vs runnumber fitting for different p_T 's: pattern 0, even crossings.

Figure 5.4: Isolated direct photon A_{LL} for signal+background (upper-left) and signal (upper-right) separated for different spin patterns and even/odd crossings, and for signal (lower-left) combined for spin patterns and crossings.

p_T [GeV]	A_{LL}	Stat. error	Syst. error
6.4231	-2.2646e-03	3.1431e-03 (138.7905%)	3.2606e-05 (1.0374%)
7.4339	2.3011e-03	4.7800e-03 (207.7270%)	3.3070e-05 (0.6918%)
8.4429	4.4489e-03	6.8512e-03 (153.9974%)	3.1239e-05 (0.4560%)
9.4503	3.8461e-03	9.4866e-03 (246.6544%)	3.2312e-05 (0.3406%)
10.8337	1.4786e-02	9.9071e-03 (67.0023%)	1.3095e-04 (1.3217%)
13.2111	1.1106e-02	1.3920e-02 (125.3304%)	1.3831e-04 (0.9936%)
16.8912	-2.0707e-02	2.1796e-02 (105.2585%)	3.9965e-04 (1.8336%)

Table 5.4: Isolated direct photon A_{LL} . The bin shift correction is applied by shifting the points along the p_T axis.

Figure 5.5: Isolated direct photon A_L^{dir} : bars statistical uncertainties and squares are systematic uncertainties.

Figure 5.6: Isolated direct photon A_{LL}^{dir} : bars statistical uncertainties and squares are systematic uncertainties. The curve and band are NLO pQCD calculations use DSSV14 polarized PDF, NNPDF3.0 unpolarized PDF and GRV FF at renormalization and factorization scales $\mu = p_T$ with the band showing 1σ uncertainty from MC replica [117–119].

could point to an unknown systematic uncertainty or overestimation of the statistical uncertainties.

5.6.1 Procedures

The spin pattern was completely randomized, separately for each fill, and then run-by-run A_{LL} was recalculated based on the new pattern. This procedure was repeated a large number of times, in this case, 40,000. Inference can be drawn from the results of the 40,000 shuffles. There is no constrain on relative luminosity in the shuffling, so, for example, if one crossing were assigned “same” helicity, the relative luminosity would be < 0.1 . Also, the statistics requirement of Eq. 5.9 was not applied for this bunch shuffling analysis.

5.6.2 Bunch Shuffling Results

We fit A_{LL} vs run for each sample with the uncertainty of each A_{LL}^{run} calculated according to the error propagation, which gives one χ_{reduced}^2 value with NDF = number of runs - 1 per iteration of the bunch shuffling. We can then check that χ_{reduced}^2 distribution agrees with the theoretical expectation. The results of bunch shuffling with even crossing number are in Fig. 5.7. χ_{reduced}^2 's have good agreement with 1 except for isolated total photons at $p_T < 4$ GeV, which was considered in systematic uncertainty study in sec 5.8.1.

5.7 Longitudinal Single Spin Asymmetry A_L Cross Check

As a cross check, we checked the longitudinal single spin asymmetry A_L 's and confirmed that they are consistent with zero. They are shown in Fig. 5.8 for blue beam and Fig. 5.9 for yellow beam.

5.8 Systematic Uncertainties for Direct Photon A_{LL}

Figure 5.7: χ^2_{reduced} distributions (black curves) for isolated total photon: even crossings. The red curves are the standard χ^2_{reduced} distributions with the same NDF, normalized by the bunch shuffling yield.

Figure 5.8: Isolated direct photon blue beam A_L for signal+background (upper-left) and signal (upper-right) separated for different spin patterns and even/odd crossings, and for signal (lower-left) combined for spin patterns and crossings.

Figure 5.9: Isolated direct photon yellow beam A_L for signal+background (upper-left) and signal (upper-right) separated for different spin patterns and even/odd crossings, and for signal (lower-left) combined for spin patterns and crossings.

5.8.1 False Asymmetry in Background due to Ghost Clusters at Low p_T

It has been reported that there might be some systematic difference between the different spin patterns in the run-by-run A_{LL} 's especially at low p_T . We attributed this effect to how the EMCal stored energy information. The effect has been noticeable since run 9 due to increased luminosity and studied in [114]. Because luminosity was increased a lot in run 13, the effect becomes more important in run 13 analysis. See [114] to get further information on how the false asymmetry occurred.

To avoid mixing false asymmetry, spin pattern separated analysis has been done. In addition to the spin pattern separate analysis, ToF cut is required for clusters to reject the ghost cluster. We got an agreement in F-test. Since the F-test and bunch shuffling shows good agreement in our interested p_T range from 6 GeV to 20 GeV, we didn't assign further systematic uncertainty for the false asymmetry.

5.8.2 Relative Luminosity

As stated in [120], the systematic uncertainty of relative luminosity is assigned as $A_{LL}^{\text{ZDC/BBC}}$, which is the A_{LL} from ZDC using BBC to calculate its relative luminosity. It was calculated as

$$A_{LL}^{\text{ZDC/BBC}} = \frac{1}{P_B P_Y} \frac{\frac{N_{\text{ZDC}}^{++}}{N_{\text{BBC}}^{++}} - \frac{N_{\text{ZDC}}^{++}}{N_{\text{BBC}}^{++}}}{\frac{N_{\text{ZDC}}^{++}}{N_{\text{BBC}}^{++}} + \frac{N_{\text{ZDC}}^{++}}{N_{\text{BBC}}^{++}}} \quad (5.12)$$

The upper limit is $\Delta A_{LL} (\text{RelLumi.}) = 3.853\text{e-}4$ for run 13. This systematic uncertainty is applied globally to all p_T bins.

5.8.3 Global Scaling Uncertainty from Polarization

As discussed in SubSec. 2.4.1 of [94], the polarization group advised using run 12 value for global systematic uncertainty on $P_B P_Y$ of 6.6%. Additional uncertainty from polarization direction is small compared to the global scaling uncertainty of polarization. Thus the uncertainty from polarization direction was ignored. The uncertainty of polarization acted as global scaling uncertainty across all p_T .

5.8.4 Yield Extraction for π^0 Background

The systematic uncertainty of π^0 yield extraction was estimated by the difference between `gaus+pol3` fitting and GPR fitting as in Sec. 4.7. Then it propagated to A_{LL} as the systematic uncertainty of the π^0 background fraction.

5.8.5 A_{LL}^η Background

Other than π^0 background, there are also photons from η , ω , η' , etc. Most of them are from η decay. A_{LL}^η was measured at $\sqrt{s} = 200$ GeV at run 5, 6 and 9 [116] and is consistent with zero. We used the combined A_{LL}^η from 200 GeV assuming x_T scaling as the central value, and varied it by quadratic sum of statistical and systematic uncertainties (TABLE VII of [116]) to propagate to A_{LL}^{dir} .

Chapter 6

Summary and Discussion

The proton spin decomposition provides valuable information to understand the structure of nucleons. The gluon spin has significant contributions to the proton spin and is important to solve the proton spin puzzle. There are two kinds of experiments probing the gluon spin: photon-gluon fusion in polarized DIS and hadron scattering in polarized proton collisions. The DIS experiments were summarized in Sec. 1.3.1, with EIC as the future opportunity.

In my thesis work, I focused on direct photon production in polarized $\vec{p} + \vec{p}$ collisions. Comparing with the production of hadrons, such as jets and charged pions, direct photon production has little fragmentation involved and is the “cleanest” channel. However, its usability to extract gluon spin contributions was limited by statistics due to the suppression of the QED coupling constant until RHIC run 13, which provides the highest integrated luminosity for polarized $\vec{p} + \vec{p}$ collisions. In addition, PHENIX has EMCAL with fine granularity such that the two π^0 decay photons can be resolved up to a $\pi^0 p_T$ of 12 GeV/c, and a shower profile analysis extends the γ/π^0 discrimination to beyond 20 GeV/c. These conditions finally made this “golden” measurement come to reality.

After introducing the experimental facility at RHIC and detector at PHENIX, I gave a detailed description of the inclusive and isolated direct photon cross section measurements (Ch. 4). The background photons were carefully analyzed and the cross section from PhSc West, PbSc East and PbGl gives consistent results (Fig. 4.29b and Fig. 4.33b). The isolation cut largely reduces the backgrounds and gives smaller systematic uncertainties (Tab. 4.6 and Fig. 4.43). The isolated direct photon cross section is well

predicted by NLO pQCD calculation (Fig. 4.34).

However, the NLO pQCD calculation underestimates the inclusive direct photon cross section by up to a factor of ~ 3 for $p_T < 12$ GeV/c (Fig. 4.30). This is due to the lack of multiparton interactions (MPI) and parton showers (PS) in the NLO pQCD calculation. POWHEG + PYTHIA8 that includes MPI and PS gives a better prediction for inclusive direct photon cross section (Fig. 4.32). The importance of including MPI and PS is also clearly shown in the isolated over inclusive direct photon cross section (Fig. 4.35).

After showing that NLO pQCD calculation gives consistent prediction for isolated direct photon cross section, we measured isolated direct photon A_{LL} and compared it with DSSV14 calculation (Fig. 5.6). We first separated the measurements for four spin patterns and even and odd crossings. After confirming the eight groups of A_{LL} are consistent with each other (Fig. 5.4), we combined them in the final result. We also checked the single spin asymmetries are consistent with zero due to parity (Fig. 5.5). The measured isolated direct photon A_{LL} will provide independent constraints on gluon spin contributions when included in the global analyses in the future.

Perspective

With previous polarized DIS [41, 121] and p+p measurements [116, 122–124], as well as the recent and future jet and hadron measurements at the STAR Collaboration [125, 126], the gluon helicity density function, $\Delta g(x)$, was probed mainly in the range $0.005 \lesssim x \lesssim 0.6$. These measurements not only confirmed that there is a positive contribution from the gluon spin to the proton spin but also suggested a nonzero contribution from the orbital angular momentum. The future upgrade of the PHENIX detector, sPHENIX [127], will improve the ability to measure the jet and heavy flavor productions. To further reduce the uncertainty (Fig. 6.1), as well as reaching below $x \lesssim 0.005$, we need a machine with polarized beams and high luminosity to provide precision spin measurements in a large kinematic range. The EIC [59], together with its upgraded detectors, will fulfill these requirements and finally help us to understand the gluon spin contribution and the proton spin decomposition.

Figure 6.1: Impact of the projected EIC A_{LL} pseudodata on the quark singlet helicity (left panel) and gluon helicity (right panel) distributions as a function of Bjorken- x for $Q^2 = 10 \text{ GeV}^2$. The uncertainty bands for DSSV14 estimate (light blue), the fit including the $\sqrt{s} = 45 \text{ GeV}$ DIS pseudodata (blue), and the reweighting with $\sqrt{s} = 140 \text{ GeV}$ pseudodata (dark blue) are also shown.

Appendix A

Calculation of Peak Position and Width of Reconstructed π^0 Mass

The measured peak of π^0 mass for a specific p_T bin is shifted up due to the energy smearing of EMCal and the steep falling true p_T distributions. The π^0 invariant mass is

$$m_{\pi^0}^2 = (p_1 + p_2)^2 = 2p_1 \cdot p_2 = 2E_1E_2(1 - \cos\theta) = 4E_1E_2 \sin^2\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right), \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where p_1 and p_2 are the four momenta of the π^0 decay photons, E_1 and E_2 are their energy, and θ is the opening angle between them. We will use superscript t (e.g. E_1^t) for true quantities and superscript r (e.g. E_1^r) for reconstructed quantities. The mean of reconstructed π^0 mass for the energy

bin $a < E_1^r, E_2^r < b$ with a Gaussian energy smearing is the following

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle m_{\pi^0}^r | a < E_1^r, E_2^r < b \rangle &= \frac{\int_a^b dE_1^r \int_a^b dE_2^r \int_0^\pi d\theta^r p(E_1^r, E_2^r, \theta^r) 2 \sin(\frac{\theta^r}{2}) \sqrt{E_1^r E_2^r}}{\int_a^b dE_1^r \int_a^b dE_2^r \int_0^\pi d\theta^r p(E_1^r, E_2^r, \theta^r)} \\
&= \frac{\int_0^\infty dE_1^t \int_0^\infty dE_2^t p(E_1^t, E_2^t) \int_a^b dE_1^r \int_a^b dE_2^r p(E_1^r, E_2^r | E_1^t, E_2^t) m_{\pi^0}^t \sqrt{\frac{E_1^r E_2^r}{E_1^t E_2^t}}}{\int_0^\infty dE_1^t \int_0^\infty dE_2^t p(E_1^t, E_2^t) \int_a^b dE_1^r \int_a^b dE_2^r p(E_1^r, E_2^r | E_1^t, E_2^t)} \\
&= m_{\pi^0}^t \frac{\int_0^\infty dE_1^t \int_0^\infty dE_2^t p(E_1^t, E_2^t) \int_a^b dE_1^r p(E_1^r | E_1^t) \sqrt{\frac{E_1^r}{E_1^t}} \int_a^b dE_2^r p(E_2^r | E_2^t) \sqrt{\frac{E_2^r}{E_2^t}}}{\int_0^\infty dE_1^t \int_0^\infty dE_2^t p(E_1^t, E_2^t) \int_a^b dE_1^r p(E_1^r | E_1^t) \int_a^b dE_2^r p(E_2^r | E_2^t)} \\
&= m_{\pi^0}^t \frac{\int_0^\infty dE_1^t \int_0^\infty dE_2^t p(E_1^t, E_2^t) \int_{a-E_1^t}^{b-E_1^t} d\delta_1 \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{\delta_1^2}{2\sigma(E_1^t)^2}\right)}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma(E_1^t)} \sqrt{1 + \frac{\delta_1}{E_1^t}} \int_{a-E_2^t}^{b-E_2^t} d\delta_2 \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{\delta_2^2}{2\sigma(E_2^t)^2}\right)}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma(E_2^t)} \sqrt{1 + \frac{\delta_2}{E_2^t}}}{\int_0^\infty dE_1^t \int_0^\infty dE_2^t p(E_1^t, E_2^t) \int_{a-E_1^t}^{b-E_1^t} d\delta_1 \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{\delta_1^2}{2\sigma(E_1^t)^2}\right)}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma(E_1^t)} \int_{a-E_2^t}^{b-E_2^t} d\delta_2 \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{\delta_2^2}{2\sigma(E_2^t)^2}\right)}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma(E_2^t)}} \\
&= m_{\pi^0}^t \frac{\int_0^\infty dE_1^t \int_0^\infty dE_2^t p(E_1^t, E_2^t) \left[\int_{\frac{a}{E_1^t}-1}^{\frac{b}{E_1^t}-1} dr_1 \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{r_1^2}{2\sigma_r(E_1^t)^2}\right)}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_r(E_1^t)} \sqrt{1+r_1} \int_{\frac{a}{E_2^t}-1}^{\frac{b}{E_2^t}-1} dr_2 \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{r_2^2}{2\sigma_r(E_2^t)^2}\right)}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_r(E_2^t)} \sqrt{1+r_2} \right]}{\int_0^\infty dE_1^t \int_0^\infty dE_2^t p(E_1^t, E_2^t) \left[\int_{\frac{a}{E_1^t}-1}^{\frac{b}{E_1^t}-1} dr_1 \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{r_1^2}{2\sigma_r(E_1^t)^2}\right)}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_r(E_1^t)} \int_{\frac{a}{E_2^t}-1}^{\frac{b}{E_2^t}-1} dr_2 \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{r_2^2}{2\sigma_r(E_2^t)^2}\right)}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_r(E_2^t)} \right]} \tag{A.2}
\end{aligned}$$

where $\delta = E^r - E^t$, $r = \delta/E^t$, and $\sigma_r = \sigma/E^t$. In the second step we used the formula of total probability. For simplicity, we assumed no position smearing and integrated out θ^r . In the last line of Eq. A.2, when $E_1^t, E_2^t < a \Rightarrow r_1, r_2 > 0$, the factor in square bracket of the numerator is larger than that of the denominator. Vice versa, this factor of the numerator is smaller than that of the denominator when $E_1^t, E_2^t > b$. Due to the steep falling of true energy distribution $p(E_1^t, E_2^t)$, the increase at low energy is larger than the decrease at high energy. As a result, the mean of reconstructed π^0 mass will be larger than the nominal value, 135 MeV/c². It turns out that for the reconstructed $p_T^{\pi^0}$ bin around 4 GeV/c, the peak of reconstructed π^0 mass in EMCAL is ~ 137 MeV/c². Note that this mass shift depends on the requirement of reconstructed energy in the energy bin $a < E_1^r, E_2^r < b$. Instead, if we require the true energy in the energy bin $a < E_1^t, E_2^t < b$ (e.g. by using the truth information from event generator in a simulation), the mean of reconstructed

π^0 mass is

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle m_{\pi^0}^r | a < E_1^t, E_2^t < b \rangle &= \int_0^\infty dE_1^r \int_0^\infty dE_2^r \int_0^\pi d\theta^r p(E_1^r, E_2^r, \theta^r | a < E_1^t, E_2^t < b) 2 \sin\left(\frac{\theta^r}{2}\right) \sqrt{E_1^r E_2^r} \\
&= \frac{\int_a^b dE_1^t \int_a^b dE_2^t p(E_1^t, E_2^t) \int_0^\infty dE_1^r \int_0^\infty dE_2^r p(E_1^r, E_2^r | E_1^t, E_2^t) m_{\pi^0}^t \sqrt{\frac{E_1^r E_2^r}{E_1^t E_2^t}}}{\int_a^b dE_1^t \int_a^b dE_2^t p(E_1^t, E_2^t)} \\
&= m_{\pi^0}^t \frac{\int_a^b dE_1^t \int_a^b dE_2^t p(E_1^t, E_2^t) \left[\frac{\int_{-1}^\infty dr_1 \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{r_1^2}{2\sigma_r(E_1^t)^2}\right)}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_r(E_1^t)} \sqrt{1+r_1} \int_{-1}^\infty dr_2 \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{r_2^2}{2\sigma_r(E_2^t)^2}\right)}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_r(E_2^t)} \sqrt{1+r_2}}{\int_{-1}^\infty dr_1 \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{r_1^2}{2\sigma_r(E_1^t)^2}\right)}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_r(E_1^t)} \int_{-1}^\infty dr_2 \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{r_2^2}{2\sigma_r(E_2^t)^2}\right)}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_r(E_2^t)}} \right]}{\int_a^b dE_1^t \int_a^b dE_2^t p(E_1^t, E_2^t)}. \tag{A.3}
\end{aligned}$$

When $\sigma \ll a \Rightarrow \sigma_r = \sigma/E^t < \sigma/a \ll 1$, the factor in the numerator of the square bracket is smaller than one due to multiplication of $\sqrt{1+r} = 1 + \frac{r}{2} - \frac{r^2}{8} + \mathcal{O}(r^3)$, while that in the denominator of the square bracket is one due to unitarity of the Gaussian distribution. As a result, the mean of reconstructed π^0 mass will slightly shift down, if we require the true energy in the energy bin $a < E_1^t, E_2^t < b$ and the smearing is small $\sigma \ll a$.

For the case of specifying the reconstructed π^0 p_T bins, the π^0 peak position and width were calculated based on Eq. A.2 and compared with fast MC simulations and data (Fig. A.1). In addition to the simplified situation in Eq. A.2, we also added an energy attenuation in PbSc or PbGl as that in the fast MC. This resulted in the drop (rise) of peak position in PbSc (PbGl). We also added a distance smearing (see Sec. 3.3) to smear the opening angle. This effect was included differently in the fast MC and resulted in the rise of the width at high p_T . We used the same true p_T distribution of π^0 and energy smearing as those in the fast MC. There were also Hisa's effect that shifts down the π^0 mass by $(-1 \pm 1 \text{ MeV})$ due to photon conversion and π^0 Dalitz decay $\pi^0 \rightarrow \gamma e^+ e^-$, a global energy shift, energy nonlinearity, and energy asymmetry cut $|\frac{E_1^\gamma - E_2^\gamma}{E_1^\gamma + E_2^\gamma}| < 0.8$ included both in the calculations and in the fast MC. Calculations agreed well with fast MC for the peak position but gave a smaller width. This is due to the shower simulation in fast MC cut-off EMCAL towers which had deposited energy below the threshold when calculating the core energy of the cluster, E_{core} . The loss of energy was corrected by a constant scaling for E_{core} to not influence the mean of the reconstructed mass, $m_{\gamma\gamma}$. However, both the cutoff and the scaling contributed to its standard deviation, $\sigma_{\gamma\gamma}$. The constant scaling simply scaled the $\sigma_{\gamma\gamma}$ by a

¹ e^+e^- pair produces smaller response in EMCAL than a photon due to shorter depth of the initiated shower and light attenuation in EMCAL tower.

Figure A.1: π^0 peak position (top) and width (bottom) vs $\pi^0 p_T$ for PbSc (left) and PbGl (right). Blue lines are from calculations based on Eq. A.2; orange lines are from fast MC simulations; red points are from MinBias data. Fast MC and data are taken from Fig. 20 of [93].

constant factor and was included in the calculations. But the cutoff effect was not included and resulted in a smaller $\sigma_{\gamma\gamma}$ in the calculations. The fast MC agreed well with data except the latter had a rise in peak position at high p_T in PbSc. This is due to the unfolding of overlapped photon showers in the EMCal and included neither in the fast MC nor in the calculations.

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